

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D1.8 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results, final version

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	951867	Acronym	5G Routes
Full Title	Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results, final version		
Start Date	01/09/2020	Duration	48 months
Project URL	https://www.5g-routes.eu		
Deliverable	D1.8		
Work Package	WP1		
Contractual due date	29/2/2024	Actual submission date	5/6/2024
Nature	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Beneficiary	VTT		
Responsible Author	Johan Scholliers		
Contributions from	Patrick Durkin, Marina Laskari, Despina Brasinika(INLECOM), Christos Skoufis (EBOS), Lasse Nykänen (Vedia), Vangelis Kosmatos (Wings), Aleksandrs Levinskis (EDI), Stella Nikolaou (CERTH), Mohamed-Cherif Rahal (Vedecom), Pierre Merdrignac (Vedecom),		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 951867

	José Rodriguez (Swarco), Anton Truljov (EVR), George Agapiou (Wings), Priit Roosipuu (TTU), Diana Krievina (LMT), Agris Amolins (PV), Andrea Castelli (Brainstorm), Daniel Larrosa (Brainstorm), Jorge Baranda (CTTC)
Peer Reviewers	Andrea Castelli (BRA), Jorge Baranda (CTTC), Miquel Payaró (CTTC)
Additional review on WP1-Wp4 deliverables	Kati Kõrbe (EEE), Priit Roosipuu (TTU)

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
v1.0	30.11.20	100%	Submitted v1.0. (as D1.7)	all
v2.0	17.12.21	100%	Submitted version	J. Scholliers
v2.1	28.2.23	100%	Updated document based on comments of reviewers, submitted to Commission	all
v2.2	13.10.23	100%	Submitted version	J. Scholliers
v2.51	8.5.24		First draft for the final version	
v3.0	31.5.24		Submitted version	

Disclaimer

The content of this document reflects only the author's view. Neither the European Commission nor CINEA are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the 5G-ROUTES consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the 5G-ROUTES Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the 5G-ROUTES Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright message

© 5G-ROUTES Consortium. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	9
2	Introduction	10
2.1	Mapping 5G ROUTES Outputs	10
2.2	Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	12
2.2.1	Scope of the Testing Framework	12
2.2.2	Relation to Other Deliverables	13
2.2.3	Deliverable Structure	14
2.3	Changes to Previous Versions of the Deliverable.....	14
3	Testing Framework Overview.....	15
3.1	Testing Framework Concept	15
3.2	Key Performance Indicators and Data Collection.....	16
3.3	Technical Performance Evaluation Framework Concept.....	17
3.3.1	General Test Process.....	17
3.3.2	Lab Trial Locations	20
3.3.3	Scenarios for the field trials	20
3.3.4	Trial Sites	21
3.3.5	Ecosystem Specific Overview	24
3.4	Business Evaluation Assessment Framework	24
3.4.1	Business Evaluation Goals	24
3.4.2	5G-ROUTES Commercialisation Validation and Acceleration Methodology.....	25
3.4.3	Business Impact Assessment Methodology	26
4	Data Collection for Use Case Trials	29
4.1	Use Cases, Test Cases and Experiments	29
4.2	Research Questions and Hypotheses	29
4.3	Data Collection Process and KPI Visualisation	29
4.3.1	Data Collection Process of the Use Cases	29
4.3.2	Data Collection Tools	31
4.4	Performance Indicators	34
4.5	Data Collection for Technical Performance Evaluation	38
4.5.1	Data Sources.....	38
4.5.2	Data Storage Formats	40
4.5.3	Data Quality Requirements	41
4.5.4	Calculation of Performance Indicators from Measured Values	42
4.6	Collection of Data for Business Validation.....	42
5	Network Key Performance Indicators and Their Data Collection	47
5.1	Data rate	47
5.1.1	Definition.....	47
5.1.2	Measurement	48
5.2	Mobility.....	48
5.2.1	Definition.....	48
5.2.2	Measurement.....	49
5.3	Handover time	49
5.3.1	Definition.....	49
5.4	Latency.....	50
5.4.1	Definition.....	50

5.4.2	Measurement	51
5.5	Jitter.....	51
5.5.1	Definition.....	51
5.5.2	Measurement.....	51
5.6	Quality of Service	51
5.7	Other performance indicators	51
6	Test Plan	52
6.1	Use Case Description and Test Cases	52
6.2	Test Preparation	53
6.2.1	Administrative and Ethical Issues	53
6.2.2	System Preparation.....	54
6.2.3	Logistic Issues	54
7	Use Case Specific Aspects.....	56
7.1	Terrestrial Ecosystem	56
7.1.1	I. See-Through Platooning.....	56
7.1.2	II. Sharing Perception and Road Hazard at the Border for Connected and Automated Driving ...	58
7.1.3	UC4.1 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming on the Go	61
7.1.4	UC4.2 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move	63
7.2	Maritime Ecosystem.....	65
7.2.1	UC5.1 Connected Logistics	65
7.2.2	UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border ...	68
8	Conclusions.....	71
9	References.....	72

List of Figures

Figure 1: Relation between D1.8 and other deliverables	13
Figure 2: KPIs in 5G-ROUTES	17
Figure 3: Timetable of lab trials and field trials in 5G-ROUTES	18
Figure 4: Border crossing between Latvia and Estonia on the E264 (in Google Maps)	21
Figure 5: Finbo trace Vuosaari-Muuga and location of Itätoukki and Länsitoukki islets (source: marinetraffic.com).	23
Figure 6: Vessel M/s Finbo Cargo from Eckerö Line (eckeroline.fi) and Arctia fairway maintenance vessel	23
Figure 7: The MAMCA methodology [33].	27
Figure 8 Phases and timeline of the business validation.	28
Figure 9: Data collection process and KPI assessment using the Tenant Web Portal.	30
Figure 10: Process for collecting and processing data.	31
Figure 11: Points of Control and Observation (PCOs) in the 5G-ROUTES project	32
Figure 12: Overview of KPI manager for on-board units	33
Figure 13: Customer Validation Survey used in 5G-ROUTES: Business Context and Problem Definition, Customer segment (persona) definition, Expected Benefits.	43

Figure 14: Solution Alignment Survey used in 5G-ROUTES..... 45

Figure 15: Handover preparation time and mobility interruption time during handover between 5G networks 50

Figure .17: Use case 5.1 illustration (source Vediafi)..... 66

Figure : Video live streaming between two ferries and between a ferry and a harbour 68

List of Tables

Table 1: Adherence to 5G ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions 10

Table 2: Overview of trial locations in 5G-ROUTES 24

Table 3: Tasks, methods and tools in commercialisation validation 26

Table 4: Use case specific technical PIs and data needed to be measured 34

Table 5: Business KPIs and data needed to determine the KPI 36

Table 6: Overview of devices in 5G-ROUTES where data at application level will be logged 40

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	5th generation
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ASC	Assisted service continuity
BCR	Benefit-Cost Ratio
BLER	Block Error Rate
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CPM	Cooperative Perception Message
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DbW	Drive By Wire
DL	Download
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
E2E	End-to-End
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
gNB	Next Generation NodeB
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMD	Head Mounting Device
IMT-2020	International Mobile Telecommunications-2020
IoT	Internet Of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
LOS	Line of Sight
MAMCA	Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis
MCC	Mobile Country Code
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple Input and Multiple Output
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNC	Mobile Network Code
MNO	Mobile Network Operator

Abbreviation / Term	Description
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks
NLOS	Non-Line of Sight
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OBU	On Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEX	Operating Expenses
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PCO	Point of Control and Observation
PDCP	Packet Data Conversion Protocol
PDV	Packet Delay Variation
PI	Performance Indicator
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PPS	Pulse Per Second
PR	Penetration Rate
PRAE	Predictive Resource Allocation of V2X Related Network Functions enabler
PRI	Penetration Rate Infrastructure
PRV	Penetration Rate Vehicle
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QoS	Quality of Service
RACH	Random Access Channel
ROI	Return on Investment
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTK	Real Time Kinematics
RTT	Round Trip Time
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
STRIA	Strategic Transport Research and Innovation Agenda
SW	Software
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
T&L	Transport and Logistics
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra High Definition
UL	Upload
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VR	Virtual Reality

Abbreviation / Term	Description
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

1 Executive Summary

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM (Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility) applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki) spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of the Testing Framework deliverables is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems. Deliverable D1.7 gave an initial description of the test framework at the start of the project. The deliverable D1.12 provided an update, including the procedures for collecting data. This deliverable D1.8 is the final version of this report and consolidates insights from the field trials' preparation, providing a reference framework for CAM services validation.

The testing framework builds on the expertise and the results of other projects, as described in D1.7 and consists of two parts: the technical performance evaluation framework and the business evaluation assessment framework. The original project plan was to use the iterative Plan-Do-Check-Act approach, including 3 cycles for the technical validation, with 2 local trial cycles and one wider large-scale trial cycle covering the whole corridor. However, due to changes in the project and delays in the availability of 5G SA roaming, only a single trial cycle is planned.

During these trials, the KPIs of each use case will be calculated, and they will illustrate how 5G capabilities and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers are leveraged and how they impact application behaviour. Both terrestrial use cases and maritime use cases will be trialled. The terrestrial use case trials will be performed near the border crossing between Estonia- Latvia. The maritime use case trials are planned to take place on vessels in the Gulf of Finland.

Further, this report describes the data collection process. Starting from the list of KPIs, which are also defined in this D1.8, the data to be collected by the different components in the trials are identified. For the technical validation, data will be collected from the network, vehicles and from the other equipment used in the project. Measurements will be performed both at application level and at transport level. At transport level, KPIs will be collected using special tools like Keysight Nemo and Qosium. The Tenant Web Portal will assist in starting the measurements and offers possibilities to upload the data at the end of the experiment and to visualise the KPIs.

The business validation process is challenged with engaging and examining the field trials with a commercial and business lens to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each ecosystem. Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment. The commercialisation validation process uses a 4-step methodology: customer validation, solutions alignment, business model selection and growth trajectory. The business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES will be based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the - adapted to the project needs – Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) methodology that will result in a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) that will evaluate in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases.

This deliverable also includes the structure of the test plan, which will be developed further for all use cases prior to starting the evaluation. Last, D1.8 describes how the different use cases plan to perform testing and provides the conclusions to be considered for the final steps of the project implementation.

2 Introduction

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki) spanning across three EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of this deliverable is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.

2.1 Mapping 5G ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D1.8</i>	<i>Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results, final version</i>	<i>This document</i>	
TASKS			
<i>T1.4 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results</i>	<i>The testing framework will entail acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technological and business validation of the use cases considering the associated service management.</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>High level description of the technological and the business validation framework</i>
	<i>The testing framework will entail acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technological and business validation of the use cases considering the associated service management.</i>	<i>3.4, 4</i>	<i>Section 3.4 describes business validation acceptance tests; quality of technical performance tests is addressed in chapter 4</i>

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<i>In particular, as far as the technological validation is concerned, we will define the procedures for collecting the data feeds from the 5G nodes, stating also how these feeds will be used and analysed by the Tenant Web Portal to produce and present the KPI values in a graphical form.</i>	4.3	<i>Section 4.3 discusses data collection processes. The Tenant Web Portal is described in D2.7.</i>
	<i>Threshold limits for the benchmarking of the results will also be defined per target KPI based on the requirements stemming from each CAM use case.</i>	N/A	<i>Target values for the KPIs are discussed in D1.2.</i>
	<i>The methodology will also define how the interaction with the CAM end-users will be achieved taking into consideration the specificities of task T1.1.</i>	4.6	<i>Section 4.6 discusses the Interaction with end-users during technical performance and business validation.</i>
	<i>The business validation process is challenged with engaging and examining the field trials with a commercial and business lens in order to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each ecosystem.</i>	3.4	<i>The methodology for the identification of solutions with the highest commercialisation potential is outlined in Section 3.4.</i>

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<p><i>Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment. The commercialisation validation process uses a 4-step methodology: customer validation, solutions alignment, business model selection and growth trajectory. The Business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES will be based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the - adapted to the project needs – Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) methodology that will result to a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) that will evaluate in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases.</i></p>	<p>3.4, 4.4, 4.6</p>	<p><i>Business validation methodology is described in Section 3.4. The business KPIs to be used for the evaluation of the business perspective of the use cases are described in Section 4.4. Questionnaires, surveys and workshop material for business validation are described in Section 4.6.</i></p>

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

2.2.1 Scope of the Testing Framework

The scope of the testing framework deliverables (D1.7, D1.12, D1.8) is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems. The testing framework consists of two parts: the technical performance evaluation framework and the business evaluation assessment framework.

The main purpose of the technical performance evaluation framework is to define the processes for data collection and analysis for the technical evaluation of the use cases in cross-border scenarios. The framework determines the data to be collected, and how the KPIs are calculated from the collected data.

The business evaluation assessment framework engages and examines the field trials with a commercial and business lens to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each ecosystem.

2.2.2 Relation to Other Deliverables

This deliverable describes the testing framework, addressing both technical performance evaluation and business validation. Figure 1 shows the relation between the work described in this deliverable and other project deliverables.

The report builds on the work described in Deliverables D1.1 [1], D1.9 [4], D1.3 [2] and D1.5 [3]. Deliverables D1.1 and D1.9 describe the use cases, scenarios and KPIs, for both technical performance and business values, and their target values. Deliverable D1.3 describes the 5G network requirements, architecture and the deployment in the trial sites. Deliverable D1.5 analyses how the use cases benefit from 5G, describes the network level KPIs and the test measurements.

From D1.1, the specific features of use cases, such as the components required, situational variables and possibility to involve test users, are to be considered when designing the methodology. The KPI targets affect the network requirements, and hence the 5G functionalities which will be included in the 5G test network at the trial sites. This work is described in D1.3. The network architecture and its deployment in the test site affects to the use case scenarios, and to the test framework. D1.5 provides initial information on how the network level KPIs must be measured.

Deliverable D1.7 [5] provided the first version of the test framework. This work was used as input for D2.7 [9] on the Tenant Web Portal and for D5.1 [8], which describes the methodology to be employed across the commercialisation and market development activities for the exploitable outputs from 5G-ROUTES. The Tenant Web Portal enables graph data presentation and provides visualisation of the KPIs. Deliverable D2.7 [9] also describes the format to be used for the collection of data.

Deliverable D1.12, was the second version of the testing framework report, and includes updates based on the work described in D5.1 and D2.7.

Deliverable D1.8 is the final version of the system and includes feedback from the preparation of the evaluation as well as includes the description of the network KPI measurements, which was described in D1.5.

Figure 1: Relation between D1.8 and other deliverables

2.2.3 Deliverable Structure

Chapter 3 gives a high-level outline of the testing framework for both the technical performance evaluation procedures and business validation. It also addresses the data collection and KPI visualisation procedures. Especially CAM automated driving use cases set requirements to the development and testing environment, which must be taken into account during testing and data collection.

Chapter 4 discusses the data collection for the use case trials. The procedures for collecting the data for the technical performance evaluation is described. The data to be collected for the technical performance evaluation and the business assessment are analysed. The involvement of users and the tools for collecting information from end-users and stakeholders are described.

Chapter 5 discusses the network KPIs and their measurement methods.

Chapter 5 gives a general overview of the test plan.

Chapter 6 gives an overview of the different use cases, of the data to be collected and on the trial locations.

Chapter 7 draws the conclusions of this report, indicates the next steps towards the assessment and the requirements to the data collection system.

2.3 Changes to Previous Versions of the Deliverable

This deliverable, D1.8, is the final version of the “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results” report. Deliverable D1.7 [5] provided the first version of the testing framework. Due to changes in the project, and due to focusing of the project on cross-border aspects, several use cases were combined and other discarded. These changes were reflected in D1.12 , the second version of the report. This document is the final document and integrates the final version of the document “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM”. The first version, D1.5, described the network KPIs and their proposed measurement. As the MNOs, who were originally part of the consortium, have left the consortium, the KPIs and their measurements were reviewed, so that they are relevant for the project and are possible to measure with the tools available by the research partners.

3 Testing Framework Overview

This section will give an overview of the framework.

The testing framework in 5G-ROUTES is based on the frameworks for the validation and benchmarking of results from previous relevant projects, including:

- 5G-SOLUTIONS [12], a 5G-PPP project using a testing framework based on the Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle [13];
- 5G-TOURS [14] and 5G-EVE [15], 5G PPP projects;
- 5G-MOBIX [16], a 5G-PPP project on cross-border CAM;
- FESTA [17];
- TRUSTS [18], a H2020 project using the same iterative approach as 5G-ROUTES.

These testing frameworks are described in D1.7 [5].

3.1 Testing Framework Concept

The original approach of the 5G-ROUTES project was based on three iterative cycles of development and testing, based on Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act approach [13]. The phases of the Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act are mapped in 5G-ROUTES as:

- **Plan:** design of the use case. During this phase both the use case and the test cases are defined.
- **Do:** development and testing in lab trials. The use case functionalities are developed and tested in laboratory conditions. In parallel the infrastructure and the required network functionalities are deployed at the trial sites. The evaluation plan for the trial phase is elaborated. The data collection and evaluation tools are validated.
- **Check:** trial execution and data collection in the trials.
- **Act:** evaluation and formulation of improvements.

For these reasons there are two types of tests in 5G-ROUTES:

- **Technical testing in lab trials.** The purpose of the lab trials is to test the functionalities and the readiness of the use cases in restricted closed areas, as well as to test the integration of the use cases with the enablers from the CAM Services Platform, which are developed in WP2 and described in D2.1 [19] and D2.9 [10]. The lab trials aim to address most of the challenges, minimize the risks and reduce the uncertainties before the large-scale field trials are set and executed.
- **Field trials** validate the capabilities of both the 5G technology and the use cases to enable their commercial exploitation. During the project the use cases will validate 5G enabling technologies' features and capabilities in the cross-border areas (i.e., Valga/Valka, Tallinn-Helsinki ferry).

During the lifetime of the project the focus of the project was changed on request by the European Commission, and this, considering also technical challenges related to the availability of 5G SA roaming, resulted in several rescheduling phases in the project. A major change in refocusing of the use cases, which are described in D1.1 [1], is the concentration on two ecosystems:

- Terrestrial ecosystem, consisting of the following use cases:
 - I. **See-through platooning.** This use case builds on UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC1.3.
 - II. **Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving.** This use case builds on UC2.1, UC3.1 and a refocused UC3.3.

III. Infotainment: Real-time virtual collaboration and gaming.

- UC4.1: 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.
- UC4.2: 3D Real-time virtual collaboration on the move.
- Maritime ecosystem, in which the following use cases are trialled:
 - UC4.1: 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.
 - UC5.1: Connected logistics.
 - UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border.

The original first set of trials with 5G NSA, which was planned for Autumn 2022, was discarded to reserve sufficient resources for 5G SA tests. Both the trials for the terrestrial and maritime ecosystems will be concentrated in 2024, when the 5G network infrastructure is available, and consists of two short trial phases:

- for the Maritime ecosystem:
 - in a first phase, the tests are concentrated on assessing the validity of the technical solution for multi-hop;
 - in the second phase the selected use cases are evaluated.
- for the Terrestrial ecosystem:
 - the first phase involves basic scenarios and is concentrated on the assessment of service disruption and to validate the interaction with the CAM Services Platform;
 - second trial run with large field trials.

The technical KPIs of each use case will be evaluated during the different trial cycles, to illustrate how 5G capabilities and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers are leveraged and how they impact application behaviour.

KPIs and their target values have been specified for the different use cases in D1.1 [1], D1.9 [4] and D1.2 [7]. The impact of 5G technologies and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers on the KPIs will be measured and quantified. A special emphasis will be placed on service continuity, especially on the disruption of the service during handovers between 5G telecom operators. Multiple cross-border scenarios will be tested in field trials, involving both terrestrial and maritime environments. Conclusions and recommendations will be drawn including recommendations for further trial validations. When possible, the impact of 5G deployment will be also analysed so to potentially allow operators to evaluate their 5G network deployment scope, pattern, and duration.

3.2 Key Performance Indicators and Data Collection

Deliverable D1.1 describes the use cases and their requirements. Based on these requirements, the required performance of the network is derived in D1.5 and the targets for the network level Performance Indicators (PIs).

In deliverables D1.9 and D1.2, for each of the use cases, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are identified to measure the success of the use cases, as well as their target values. KPIs are both defined at application level for the technical performance and related to business aspects., as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: KPIs in 5G-ROUTES

The following types of KPIs can be identified:

- **Network level PIs**, which are agnostic to the use cases. The targets for these network PIs are calculated so that the use case target KPIs can be fulfilled. Network PIs and their measurements are described in D1.5 [3]. In this document, the measurements for the network KPIs, as they will be performed in the terrestrial and maritime environments, will be described (Chapter 5).
- Use case specific **technical KPIs**. Starting from the data collected during the use case trials, PIs for assessing the technical performance at service level are calculated, such as latencies of the different legs of the 5G delivery chain. The value of the PI may depend upon the configuration of the 5G network, the enablers used and potentially environmental variables (such as weather) and situational variables, such as the speed of the vehicles. Special attention will also be put on the effect of border crossing and handover. The framework for collecting and analysing the data is described in section 3.3. PIs, which are identified as important for the evaluation of the technical performance of the use case, are fed as KPIs into the Tenant Web Portal [9]. These indicators are compared to target values, set in D1.2 [7], and provide the satisfaction level of the KPIs. The satisfaction level of different indicators is then combined to form a Composite Indicator, which represents the satisfaction level for the use case, and these are visualised in the Tenant Web Portal. The results of the evaluation during the different trial phases will be reported in D4.6.
- **Business KPIs**, which are calculated from input obtained from stakeholder interactions, such as focus groups and interviews. The framework for business validation is described in section 3.4. The results of the business assessment will be reported in D5.2.

3.3 Technical Performance Evaluation Framework Concept

The data needed for the technical performance evaluation will be collected at local sites and the large-scale tests, and potentially at the lab trials, dependent on the nature of the use case and the availability of resources (network functionalities, vehicles, infrastructure sensors).

3.3.1 General Test Process

There are two sets of lab trial runs and one set of field trials in 5G-ROUTES:

- Lab trial#1 in 2022, when preparing the use cases for the 5G NSA field trial run, which was planned in 2022, but cancelled due to refocusing of the project.
- Lab trial#2 in 2023 and 2024, when preparing for the field trials which take place in Summer and Autumn 2024.

Figure 3: Timetable of lab trials and field trials in 5G-ROUTES

3.3.1.1 Test Process Phases

The process for technical performance testing consists of the following phases:

- During use case development, each use case integrates logging of the data at transport and/or application level. APIs are made available for uploading of the data to the Tenant Web Portal, which is described in D2.7 [9]. The data are either uploaded using the Tenant Web Portal functionality or manually.
- During the first set of lab tests, the different functionalities of the use case are verified. Verification takes place in 5G test networks, close to the developers’ facilities, or in commercial 4G/5G networks. The data collection mechanisms are validated.
- The pilot readiness for the planned 5G NSA trials was verified at the end of the lab trial phase in Spring 2022, through assessment that all the equipment, data communications and logging, software and algorithms are working as planned. Remote verification techniques are used to check the interfaces between the different components and the access to the networks at the large-scale trial sites. The results of the first round of lab trials and field operational readiness are reported in D3.8.
- A second run of lab trials took place in 2023 and lasts until June 2024. During these lab trials, focus is on the integration of the use cases with CAM service backends and the enablers of the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform, as well as on testing the use cases in the cross-border environment. The second run of lab trials is reported in D3.10.
- Field trials are performed in Q2 and Q3 of 2024. The first phase of the 5G SA field trials will be concentrated on detailed measurement for basic functionalities of the use cases, especially regarding the cross-border behaviour. More details on the trial sites are provided in Section 3.3.4. The test cases, which will be tested in the field trials are reported in D4.1 [11]. Network level KPIs are collected using the measurement methods reported in this deliverable. During the trial, experiments are performed and data for the technical performance evaluation are collected. The trials are reported in D4.5. Based on the collected data, the use case specific technical PIs are calculated, and the evaluation results will be reported in D4.6.

3.3.1.2 *Baseline and Impact of Configurations*

The main aim of the technical performance evaluation is to test the impact of 5G and the solutions developed by 5G-ROUTES on the integrated CAM use cases. Technical performance evaluations measure the improvement of new technology and tools compared to a baseline situation.

The baseline for the terrestrial use cases is the case without the deployed CAM Services Platform. For this purpose, the CAM services and the enablers which are essential to perform the use case will be deployed on the cloud or at servers outside of the mobile network.

During technical performance evaluation, different network configurations may be tested, e.g., the use of slicing for reserving resources for different use case functionalities, and the impact of technological choices on the performance of the use cases will be monitored.

3.3.1.3 *Test Logistics*

The nature of the use cases, i.e., cross-border CAM including automated driving, poses additional challenges to the testing. Cross-border 5G scenarios involve networks of two different MNOs. Border crossings are not located near the research and development facilities, hence on-site testing involves travelling of both research personnel and the equipment, such as the research vehicle prototypes.

Another issue is the frequency of border crossings, especially for maritime traffic. For road crossings, vehicles can be driven over a cross-border route, which crosses the border multiple times within a short period of time. Ferries, however, have a fixed timetable and cross the border only a few times a day (e.g., Eckerö Finbo travels 3 times per day between Helsinki and Tallinn).

For the trials of the automated driving use cases, prototype vehicles are used, and the possibility to perform automated driving tests at the test site are limited. For these reasons, initial testing of the use cases is performed at facilities, to which the researchers have easy access, and then validated at the cross-border sites.

The performance of the trials may pose several logistical issues, such as:

- trial demonstrations are resource intensive. They involve expensive equipment which must be brought on site by the project partners, such as instrumented vehicles, requiring time and resources for travel to the trial site. The first phase of the trials will use preliminary scenarios, concentrating on 5G connectivity. Instead of an On-Board Unit (OBU) integrated in vehicles, equipment which can be easily placed in vehicles from other partners or rental vehicles will be used. In addition, the preliminary scenarios involve only one vehicle with 2 OBUs in a single vehicle or one moving and one static OBU. For maritime tests, renting boats for testing is both expensive and requires additional personnel. Maritime tests will be first tested on land in 5G test networks.
- testing of automated driving requires permits for operation of the vehicle on public roads in both Estonia and Latvia, as well as the permit of the local authorities to use the road. Hence, to avoid this issue, automated operation of the vehicles will be performed as much as possible on closed roads. To be able to test automated driving safely and to be able to perform frequent handover events, a virtual border has been set up at the Bikernieki racetrack in Riga, which is closed to public traffic.
- some automated vehicles use cases cannot be safely demonstrated in winter. Snow and ice affect the dynamic behaviour of the vehicle, and reduce the visibility of lane and road markings, on which vehicle sensors rely.

Hence, automated operation of the vehicles must be performed on closed roads. The closure of the road must be agreed with the respective authorities. Discussions were performed with the Estonian and Latvian authorities on the possibility to close the road for automated driving tests. However, as the road crossing the border is a

major international road, and there is no easy alternative, the authorities were not willing to close the road for performing the tests. Hence, trials involving automated driving cannot be performed at the actual border in Valga-Valka, and automated driving tests will only be performed at the virtual border in Bikernieki.

3.3.2 Lab Trial Locations

The lab trial locations are described in D1.7 [5]. The results of the lab tests are reported in D3.8 and D3.10.

The main purpose of the lab trials is to assure that the use cases work when deployed at the trial sites. During the first set of lab trials, mostly locations near to the facilities of the use case developers are used. These include:

- Bikernieki racetrack, Latvia;
- Pirkkala karting track and VTT 5G test network in Otaniemi and Oulu, Finland;
- Satory, France;
- CTTC testbed in Barcelona, Spain;
- TTU 5G testbed in Tallinn, Estonia.

To test the use cases in a lab environment, the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform is deployed in CTTC and TTU 5G testbeds. Actually, the environment set for the CAM Services Platform in TTU replicates the one in CTTC to speed up its configuration and troubleshooting and it will be the environment connected to the 5G mobile network setup used for the field trials. The integration of the use cases with the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform is tested remotely during the second lab trial run.

3.3.3 Scenarios for the field trials

The use cases of the project, described in D1.1 [1], are combined in two ecosystems, as mentioned in Section 3.1. In both ecosystems, the maritime and the terrestrial ecosystem, field trials will be executed in two phases. The first phase consists of preliminary scenarios, in which the basic functionalities of the use cases are tested, with focus on service continuity and validation of the network solution. The preliminary scenarios include:

1. The Maritime ecosystem will implement a technical solution for multi-hop. It is tested using fixed network and a single User Equipment (UE), with exchange of video between the UE in the network and a fixed node. The network and the use case scenarios are first tested in 5G test networks on land near VTT premises in Otaniemi.
2. The Terrestrial ecosystem consists of 4 use cases, as mentioned in Section 3.1. For the first set of trials, only the basic functionalities of the use cases will be tested. Focus in the first trials is on assessment of service continuity and service disruption when crossing the border. These are the considerations for the different use cases:
 - **I. See-through platooning.** The use case relies on CAM services, which follow the leading UE when crossing the border. So, when the leading UE of a fleet crosses the border, the CAM service has been proactively instantiated in the visiting network. The data exchanged consists of both video (UC1.3) and short V2X data packets which are transmitted every 50-100 ms (UC1.1, UC1.2). For this first use case, the tests in the first trial will be concentrated on the exchange of video between a UE crossing the border and another UE, using the enablers from the CAM Services Platform and a video proxy CAM service.
 - **II. Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving.** The data exchanged between the different UEs and the CAM Services Platform are V2X messages transmitted every 100 ms (similar to the data exchanged in UC1.1 and UC1.2). The tests in the first trial will hence consist of exchanging V2X messages between UEs in the different networks. The use case makes use of location-dependent CAM services, e.g., for situational awareness, which should

communicate with the UE in identical way at both sides of the border and should provide the same level of service to the UE at both sides of the border.

- **UC4.1 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming on the Go.** The preliminary scenario deals with transmission of gaming data between game server and a single UE (smart phone or tablet) crossing the border. A main difference to the other preliminary scenarios is that the UE does not have the advanced position and timing capabilities of the automotive UEs.
- **UC4.2 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move.** The preliminary scenario deals with transmission of stereoscopic video data between a streaming fixed station and a receiving moving laptop with a connected head mounted display (HMD). A main difference to the other preliminary scenarios is that the UE employed does not have positioning capabilities and will employ network positioning data.

In Chapter 7, a brief overview of both the preliminary scenarios and the use-case test scenarios for each of the use cases is given. The test cases are described in more detail in D4.1 [11].

3.3.4 Trial Sites

3.3.4.1 Road Border Crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga

The E264 crosses the border between Latvia and Estonia in the twin city of Valga/Valka. Figure 4 shows the border crossing of the E264 (Rujienas street (LV)). Near the border crossing there is an intersection: the motorway continues to the left (Transpordi street) in Figure 4, and the road to the right (Viljandi street) leads to the centre of Valga. The E264 motorway is a two-way road with one lane in each direction without central barrier. The other border crossings between Latvia and Estonia in Ikla and Tsiiruli are on similar two-way roads.

Figure 4: Border crossing between Latvia and Estonia on the E264 (in Google Maps)

For the use case II, intelligent traffic lights have been installed at intersections of the E264: at the intersection Rujienas street – Viljandi street – Transpordi street in Estonia, and at the intersection of Rujienas-Ausekla street on the Latvian side. The test site is described in more detail in D3.1, section 4.2 [22].

For testing these use cases, the following conditions need to be fulfilled:

- the road must be suitable for testing of the use cases (e.g., required amount number of lanes), and sufficiently long length to be able to perform the manoeuvre;
- the area should be covered by the 5G communication infrastructure;

5G Network Configuration

The network in Valga/Valka is developed taking the needs of the project into account and is described in more detail in D3.11.

Test Vehicles

Prototype vehicles will be provided by EDI, VEDECOM and VTT. The vehicles are equipped with On-Board Units (OBUs) with 5G communications, environmental perception sensors and the vehicles have automated driving capabilities. During the trials, OBUs provided by partners may be installed in vehicles from EDI or in rental vehicles to test 5G communications for CAM. An overview of the vehicles is provided in D3.3 [23].

Trialling CAM in Valga

All use cases from the terrestrial ecosystem will be trialled in Valga.

3.3.4.2 Riga Bikernieki Racing circuit

A virtual border is set up in the Bikernieki Racing circuit in Riga. Both LMT and Telia Estonia have installed a 5G-base station at the racing circuit during the initial phase of the project. This allows to test handover between networks, provided that the base stations have access to TTU's core in Tallinn. The test site equipment is described in more detail in D3.1 [22].

Use case I (See-through platooning) may be evaluated in Bikernieki.

3.3.4.3 Maritime tests in the Gulf of Finland

The maritime tests are performed in several phases:

- the first tests will take place in Otaniemi (Espoo, Finland), using 2 vans (one from Vedia and one from VTT). The base stations of the 2 private networks will be installed in the vehicles, and the multi-hop concept will be tested. Both the network behaviour and the use cases will be tested in this configuration
- the first tests in maritime environment are planned to be performed using one vessel and a static base station, located on an islet (Itätoukki or Länsitoukki) near the Vuosaari-Muuga fairway.

Figure 5: Finbo trace Vuosaari-Muuga and location of Itätoukki and Länsitoukki islets (source: marinetrtraffic.com).

- the final tests are planned to be performed using two vessels near Vuosaari harbour: the Finbo ferry from Eckerö Line and a fairway maintenance vessel from Arctia.

Eckerö Line operates two vessels between Helsinki and Tallinn for both passengers and freight: M/S Finlandia, between the Länsisatama port in Helsinki and the A-Terminal in Tallinn, and M/S Finbo Cargo, between Vuosaari port, on the outskirts of Helsinki, and the port of Muuga Harbour near Tallinn. M/S Finbo is mainly targeted towards freight transport but can also carry 300 passengers. The vessel makes daily 2-3 trips between Helsinki and Tallinn in each direction.

Figure 6: Vessel M/s Finbo Cargo from Eckerö Line (eckeroline.fi) and Arctia fairway maintenance vessel

5G Network Configuration

Two different configurations will be tested, as described in D1.2 [7]:

- Finbo vessel between Arctia vessel and shore. The connectivity equipment, including the 5G SA private network base station, OneWeb satellite receiver, 5G NSA connection to the Telia Finland network on shore, will be installed on Finbo. Arctia connects to the larger vessel over private network, and the Finbo equipment relays the data through the 5G NSA or satellite.

- B. Arctia vessel between Finbo vessel and shore, relaying the traffic from Finbo. Arctia has also a 5G NSA connection to shore.

The equipment, which will be used to demonstrate multi-hop, will be described in more detail in D1.13.

Use Case Testing on the Ferry

The use cases from the Maritime Ecosystem will be evaluated on the ferry:

- **UC5.1 Connected logistics**
- **UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border**
- **UC4.1 Immersive 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go**

3.3.5 Ecosystem Specific Overview

Table 2 gives an overview of the tests for the different use cases and clusters, giving a summary of the vehicles which have to be brought to the trial site, the location of the lab trials, the nature of the trial, and the location of trials.

Table 2: Overview of trial locations in 5G-ROUTES

UC	UC title	Vehicle Provider	Lab test	Trials
Terrestrial Ecosystem				
I.	See-through platooning and logistics	EDI, VTT	Bikernieki, VTT-Otaniemi	Valga/Valka and Bikernieki
II.	Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving	VEDECOM, VTT, EDI	Versailles, Tampere, TTU	Valga/Valka
4.1	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go	BRA	Barcelona	
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go			
Maritime Ecosystem				
5.1	Connected logistics	Vediafi Eckerö – ferry	Vedia lab/ Otaniemi Tallinn	Ferry Helsinki (Vuosaari) – Tallinn (Muuga)
5.2	Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border	Eckerö – ferry	WINGS lab/ Otaniemi	
4.1	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go	Eckerö – ferry	Barcelona / VTT-Otaniemi	

3.4 Business Evaluation Assessment Framework

3.4.1 Business Evaluation Goals

The business validation process in 5G-ROUTES faces the challenge of engaging and scrutinising the field trials through a commercial and business lens. This approach is crucial for identifying those solutions with the highest potential for commercial viability and delivering the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders of the two 5G-ROUTES ecosystems; the maritime and the terrestrial.

The business validation process is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment.

The primary goal for **the commercialisation validation process** in WP5 is to create anticipatory business plans for two solutions, each tailored to one of the two ecosystems, that extend 5G at different cross-border environments. A customer-focused, collaborative, and iterative process has been designed to guide the solution providers from initial ideas through potential business impacts, demonstrating how commercial actors supporting the ecosystems can bring those outputs closer to commercial reality.

For the **business impact assessment**, the consortium is working upon the two defined ecosystems (maritime and terrestrial), to collect the required data during stakeholder workshops and interviews. The collected data will encompass both quantitative (i.e., costs) and qualitative aspects, as reflected by the selected Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) business criteria. The cost benefit analysis and business impact assessment will be formulated based on future penetration scenarios of the most promising business opportunities validated. The final outcome of T5.2 will be to deliver the estimated impact and cost-benefit for the developed ecosystems, validated by both internal and external to the project stakeholders. Furthermore, leveraging the 5G Architecture and 5G CAM Infrastructure developed within the project, we will investigate the interoperability impact and deployment potential in close collaboration with the project technology providers.

Further details about the business validation methodology and results will be reported in the new deliverable D5.2 (merged D5.2 and D5.3) titled “Business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems”.

The overall business validation methodology includes several key activities and actions aimed at providing practical commercial recommendations to the consortium and the 5G for CAM European community:

- i. conduct a detailed assessment of broad market opportunities and the evolving technological, financial and social environment surrounding 5G and cross-border networking aspects;
- ii. undertake an analysis of the business opportunities for the two 5G ROUTES ecosystems (maritime and terrestrial);
- iii. develop two business propositions (one for each ecosystem: maritime and terrestrial) focusing on making 5G a reliable and high-quality technology even at the border between two countries and administrative domains;
- iv. evaluate the value propositions for the two ecosystems through stakeholder workshops (one for each ecosystem) to identify the priority areas for the cost-benefit analysis;
- v. perform business impact assessment and cost-benefit analyses for the two ecosystems supported by stakeholder ecosystems’ interviews;
- vi. assign each commercial service with a lead commercialisation partner around whom the business development plan that is created within 5G-ROUTES can be centred;
- vii. thoroughly explore each ecosystem to understand key dynamics around revenue, cost, investment etc. and prepare the final business models for potential implementation post project completion.

It is important to note that Innovation Management plays a supporting role in business validation by helping partners to identify the unique value proposition along with the potential competitive advantage and business prospect of innovative ideas. These ideas are documented in the Innovation Registry (a tool for facilitating Innovation Management), where it is linked with potential business benefits (e.g., cost-efficiency, increased market reach, new functionalities, improved quality of service, etc). Furthermore, through IP Protection and the patenting process -the filing of 4 patents is funded through 5G-ROUTES- innovative ideas are legally protected, thus restricting competition in the specific domain. The methodology and results of the Innovation Management and IP (Intellectual Property) protection is reported in D5.5 “Innovation Management Plan and IP protection report v1.0” and in D5.6 “Innovation management plan and IP protection report final version”.

3.4.2 5G-ROUTES Commercialisation Validation and Acceleration Methodology

In the context of European Research Projects, consortia face several challenges compared to standalone, individual start-ups, which typically focus on addressing specific problems within a narrow customer segment and grow outwards from initial pilot implementations to long-term viability. EU research projects, by their nature, necessitate a broader perspective that encompasses a range of views and expertise to finally arrive at a body of knowledge with transformative potential for the future of EU citizens. **Nonetheless, the primary**

challenge lies in maintaining research efforts focused on creating solutions that create value for real stakeholders.

Table 3 provides a high-level overview of the 4 pillars of the methodology and the process involved in progressing towards a validated, commercially viable plan for those opportunities that are the most commercially attractive. The table summarises the specific tasks, methods and tools employed in each phase.

Table 3: Tasks, methods and tools in commercialisation validation

Goal	Create a body of work that provides a realistic roadmap for the commercialisation of outputs from the 5G-ROUTES research project that are customer oriented, validated and supported by commercially motivated consortium partners.			
Phase	Customer Validation	Solution Alignment	Business Model Selection	Growth Trajectory
Key Question	Segment and refine specific customer wants and needs	Define and align potential product(s) to target market	Select most appropriate business model to acquire and retain profitable customers	Articulate a business plan for growth and sustainability
Key Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market / stakeholder analysis and segmentation Ecosystem focused customer validation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agree product(s) to commercialise/exploit with commercial leader(s) Define product and service portfolio Alignment with Innovation Registry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examine range of potential models Align business model to commercial leader and early adopters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roadmaps – financial, people, product, marketing, sales, funding
Methods and Tools	Desk research, Solution provider interviews and surveys	Desk research, PESTLE analysis, Innovation Registry, Product definition workshops with commercial leaders	Business model canvas, Value proposition canvas, Business model workshops	Financial templates, commercial leader Interviews

3.4.3 Business Impact Assessment Methodology

The Business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES is based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the – adapted to the project needs – MAMCA methodology. This is resulting in a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a **Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)** that is evaluating in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases. The involvement of the internal and external stakeholders identified preliminarily in D1.1 and D1.9 and revisited within WP5 will serve a major role in the process. The results of this work will be reported in D5.2.

The business impact indicators have been recreated to focus more on the 5G technology improvements for the two project ecosystems. This is a part of the Step 3 of the MAMCA methodology (see below Figure 7) that feed the CBA for the in-depth analysis. The MAMCA methodology uses as its main tool physical stakeholder workshops (see Section 4.6.1.2) for each identified business ecosystem, in order to weigh the business criteria at first and then to rank the value propositions against those criteria. Two physical stakeholder workshops have been realised to evaluate the VPs created for each project ecosystem (maritime and terrestrial).

The MAMCA [24] methodology allows to assess and prioritise a set of alternatives (measures, scenarios,

strategies, technological solutions etc.), taking into consideration the opinion of experts as well as the preferences of stakeholders. Apart from resulting in the final prioritisation of the proposed alternatives, the MAMCA methodology allows the understanding of the view of each stakeholder cluster regarding the problem and aims at determining an optimum compromise between the different and usually conflicting stakeholders' interests.

The different steps of the MAMCA methodology are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: The MAMCA methodology [32].

CBAs are often used to support decision-making in the context of large-scale infrastructure projects where actual measured data can be gathered during a longer period of time and the piloting phase also provides information about various cost categories during the trial.

For the project CBA t, qualitative and explorative methodology has been used in addition to tangible data, in order to investigate the potential of the 5G technology in the CAM markets. To support the qualitative analysis, a set of additional tools have been used (see Section 4.6) to facilitate the process, encompassing expert-based ranking following the Delphi¹ method. Such data will be also processed to the sensitivity analysis in order to better define social benefits. This viewpoint emphasizes the significance of identifying solutions for interoperability and potential operators for data-driven services.

As a summary, Figure 8 shows the updated timeline and the different phases of both the commercialisation validation (blue) and the business impact assessment (green).

¹ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/delphi-method.asp>

Figure 8 Phases and timeline of the business validation.

4 Data Collection for Use Case Trials

4.1 Use Cases, Test Cases and Experiments

The Tenant Web Portal, described in D2.7 [9], will be used for the data storage. The Tenant Web Portal database for collected raw data is structured as follows:

1. Use cases and agnostic data:
 - a. network data is stored in a flat structure in the Tenant Web Portal, and PIs are measured, according to D1.5, for the different networks;
 - b. use cases are characterised by the identifiers previously used, such as UC4.1.
2. Test Cases: for each of the use cases, a set of test cases are defined in D4.1 [11]. From measurement viewpoint, a test case is characterised by the following parameters:
 - i. network configuration(s) used in the test. For cross-border tests this includes 2 networks;
 - ii. use of enablers, including edge, slicing as well as the technical enablers of the CAM Service Platform, developed in 5G-ROUTES;
 - iii. test conditions, including traffic status (test route, SIM cards used, road users involved in the test, target speeds), environmental conditions (road weather, vegetation...).
3. Experiments: each test case is repeated several times, under exactly the same conditions.

4.2 Research Questions and Hypotheses

For each of the use cases, a set of target KPIs has been defined in D1.2 [7]. The main research questions addressed in 5G-ROUTES are related to the capability of 5G network and the 5G-ROUTES enablers to reach the target KPI in cross-border environments, and to assure the service continuity without disruption when crossing borders. The main research questions and hypotheses for the various use cases are addressed in Chapter 7.

4.3 Data Collection Process and KPI Visualisation

4.3.1 Data Collection Process of the Use Cases

For the technical performance evaluation, data will be collected from the different UEs and components, such as vehicles and application servers involved in the use case trials.

The Tenant Web Portal, which is developed during the 5G-ROUTES project, will be used for storage of the data and for visualising the KPI results [9]. The use of the Tenant Web Portal is considered as an important element to 5G-ROUTES to automate and accelerate the execution of the use cases running in parallel. The Tenant Web Portal is also used for the analysis, benchmarking, and presentation of the technical Performance Indicators from cross-border field trials. The Tenant Web Portal allows, by using big-data graph analytics and cloud-computing, rapid and automated processing of the vast amount of data obtained from the trials.

The actual raw test data will be stored in the Tenant Web Portal or by the partner responsible for the test (use case leader for use case specific tests). Test data with assured quality which has been used for evaluation, will be made available after the project in public repositories like Zenodo.

The Tenant Web Portal will offer the following functionalities [9]:

- Use case setup: making network resources (computing, memory, storage) available for the execution of the use case prior to the actual tests. This includes the instantiation of the CAM services and the assignment of a unique test identifier for the experiment.

- Data storage. The Tenant Web Portal contains a database with both general information on the tests performed, the raw test data collected and the PIs.
- Data collection and storage: Data for the agnostic network measurements is collected using specific tools by the network operators. For the use case specific tests, data can be collected in two ways:
 - automated data collection. The Tenant Web Portal contains an MQTT client, connected to the Integration Fabric enabler described in D2.1 [19], which can inform to the use case devices when the experiment starts and stops. At the end of the experiment, data collected during an experiment can be automatically uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal. More information on this functionality is provided in D2.7 [9].
 - manual data collection. Data is collected locally at the different devices and components involved in the CAM trials. After each specific experiment – or alternatively after the test case or at the end of the day, data is manually uploaded to Tenant Web Portal.
- Data download functionality. Use case leaders can download the data collected for quality assurance and analysis.
- KPI input functionality: the test responsible enters the values of the KPIs in the Tenant Web Portal.
- The KPIs are visualised in the Tenant Web portal: the composite indicators, defined in D1.9 [4], are calculated in the Tenant Web Portal, using targets set by the use case leaders, and visualised in a spider graph.

Figure 9 gives an overview of the interaction of the end user (e.g., use case leader) with the Tenant Web Portal during data collection and visualisation process.

Figure 9: Data collection process and KPI assessment using the Tenant Web Portal.

The complete process flow for data collection and processing is shown in Figure 10. The process consists of:

- prior to testing: deployment of the use case in the trial site;
- the experiments are set up in the Tenant Web Portal, consisting of the instantiation of virtualised CAM service backend for the use case;
- the experiments are executed, and the results are either stored locally, or automatically stored in the Tenant Web Portal at the end of each experiment. If the data is stored locally, the use case leader uploads the data manually to the Tenant Web Portal e.g., at the end of the day, after a quality check. Metadata regarding the test is stored (e.g., environmental conditions, specific observations regarding the test);

- after the test session, the data are downloaded from the Tenant Web Portal, and the data are analysed by the partner responsible for the evaluation of the use case;
- the KPIs for the experiments are then fed into the Tenant Web Portal and the composite indicators visualised;
- for each test case, the aggregated KPIs are calculated based on the KPIs of the different experiments in the Tenant Web Portal.

Figure 10: Process for collecting and processing data.

4.3.2 Data Collection Tools

Data logging in 5G networks can be performed at different OSI-layers, and the measured performance indicator (e.g., the latency) depend on the OSI-layer and the location of the Points of Control and Observation (PCOs). A PCO is a specific point within the system under test, at which either an observation (measurement) is recorded, or traffic is injected. The PCOs are located at the relevant communication interfaces and can be organized in levels. The 5G-MOBIX [16] project defines the following 3 levels for PCOs:

- Level 0, Access level: at this PCO level, information is collected about the radio access network parameters. These measurements are performed with tools provided by the modem or chipset vendor. This PCO allows taking measurement of the cellular network, such as Mobile Network Code (MNC), Mobile Country Code (MCC), signal strength and quality, and the protocol message exchange. It will allow to identify when a handover is taking place;
- Level 1, transport: at IP network/transport layer, using IP connectivity. This level allows evaluating QoS indicators (such as TCP/IP or UDP/IP throughput, UL and DL, one-way delay, packet loss, etc.) and monitoring the traffic received. This level can be implemented at both the UE side and the network side (edge/core);
- Level 2, application level: this is the level where messages are exchanged with the application. Measurements directly integrated in the application, e.g., end-to-end latency, user experienced data rate.

In the 5G-ROUTES project, the following PCOs are used:

- Level 0: measurements at the modems, using software from UE or chipset vendors, e.g., using the APIs provided by the UE or chipset APIs, or special tools such as Keysight Nemo;
- Level 1: software installed at the UEs and at application servers, monitoring the IP traffic. Tools include Qosium, Vedecom KPI Manager, tcpdump and Wireshark;
- Level 2: logging integrated in the application software at the UEs, cloud and at edge applications and enablers developed within 5G-ROUTES project.

Figure 11: Points of Control and Observation (PCOs) in the 5G-ROUTES project

4.3.2.1 Qosium

Qosium, a product of the Finnish company Kaitotek Oy, is a real-time passive network performance measurement solution [31]. It is a product for PCO level 1 and performs real-time QoS and QoE measurements over wireless and wired networks. It allows to monitor and visualise several QoS KPIs (e.g., UL/DL TCP/UDP throughput, network delay, packet error rate etc.) from the sender and receiver viewpoint.

Qosium is used for measuring the traffic flowing between two points in the network path. Qosium makes use of two major components: Qosium Probe and Qosium Scope. Qosium Probe is a measurement agent which is directly installed in a measurement point, operates in the background in the platform where it is installed as system service, and performs most of the measurement functionalities, like packet capturing and results calculation. Qosium Scope is a measurement controller and collects and visualised the results [31].

Qosium Probe and Scope can be installed in various platforms, permitting to take single or multi-point measurements. The traffic statistics are then collected in CSV format files, allowing to import the data to other platforms such as Microsoft Excel. Typically, values are monitored as averaged values over the user-defined averaging interval.

4.3.2.2 VEDECOM KPI Manager

VEDECOM has developed several modules for monitoring and capturing metrics at the different network level for testing and validating CAM applications. As illustrated in Figure 12, VEDECOM's KPI manager tool is composed of different components embedded on the 5G OBU for observation of metrics at multiple layers:

- Access Manager is collecting access metrics by querying network information on the 5G modem;
- Network Aggregation Manager is collecting network metrics from the capture of packets on the network interfaces;
- V2X Statistics Manager can provide statistics on the V2X services (cooperative awareness, decentralized event notification, collective perception) by collecting information on exchanged messages.

Figure 12: Overview of KPI manager for on-board units

In addition, these modules can send online measurements on the target indicators to a KPI capture tool via common log data messages. Then, these logs can be stored into a database for further analysis and visualisation.

In the context of 5G-ROUTES, the logs collected through these components should be uploaded either online or offline on the Tenant Web Portal for evaluation of use case performances.

4.3.2.3 Keysight Nemo

Keysight Nemo Outdoor 5G NR Drive Test Solution [33] is a software tool for laptops for wireless network testing. Keysight Nemo will mainly be used in the project to assess the performance of the control plane. This notably includes measurements related to application state transitions during handover. During handover information can be retrieved including:

- Handover (HO) type (NR handover between cells, NR handover between frequencies, NR handover between bands, NR handover between systems);
- Source/Target cellular system;
- Source/Target band;
- Source/Target channel;
- Source/Target cell id;
- Measurement event (A1-A6, B1-B2) [34];
- Handover duration (with the LTE and NR this defines the handover duration containing handover processing and interrupt time. Time from the handover initiating RRC (Radio Resource Control) signalling message to the successfully completed RACH (Random Access Channel) procedure in the new cell);
- Handover User-plane interruption time (time from the last packet in the old cell to the first packet in the new cell);
- Roaming status (roaming or not roaming).

Nemo runs on a laptop and sets specific requirements to the UE, e.g. requires access to the diagnostic port of the modem, hence the 5G modem used for the Nemo tests may be different from the 5G modem used for the use case execution.

4.3.2.4 Tcpdump and Wireshark

Tcpdump is a network packet analyser and protocol analysis tool. Tcpdump is launched from the command line. It can be used to analyse network traffic by intercepting and displaying packets that are being created or received

by the computer it is running on. Tcpdump is hence a powerful tool for resolving network issues. Tcpdump can also capture whole packages and save them in libpcap format as pcap files.

Wireshark is an open-source network protocol analyser. It is used for network troubleshooting, analysis, software and communications protocol development, and education. Through filters, e.g., for the source or target IP-address, Wireshark saves only the packets of interest. Wireshark can be operated either from a graphical user interface or direct from the command line. Wireshark captured data is stored in the pcapng file format, and also supports the libpcap format, which is used by tcpdump. Wireshark can also be used to analyse the pcap files captured by tcpdump.

In order to get KPIs from pcap files, collected either through tcpdump or Wireshark, scripts are needed to extract the relevant messages, and perform calculations. KPIs which could be calculated include e.g., service disruption time during handover. For the calculation of KPIs related to performance of network, e.g., packet loss or latency, pcap files have to be collected at both the transmitting and receiving nodes, and scripts developed to compare both files.

4.3.2.5 Getting data from User Equipment

In order to get information on the network, to which the UE is connected, commands which are specific to the chipset, which is used by UE, are needed. These commands may be integrated in the tools which are mentioned in the previous subsections. If not, collecting the information through AT commands must be integrated with the logging software at application level.

4.4 Performance Indicators

The PIs and KPIs are described in more detail in D1.9 [4] and D1.5 [3]. D1.5 addresses the definition of the tests for network level PIs. The PIs are repeated here to analyse which data is needed to be collected, and to assess the requirements for the data collection process, especially for the technical performance evaluation.

Performance Indicators (PI) can be divided in different categories:

- **Network level PIs** are described in more detail in Chapter 5. These performance indicators are use case agnostic and are measured using synthetic data.
- **Use case specific technical PIs** are related to the service level performance for the use cases. The use case specific technical PIs are summarized in Table 4 and described in more detail in Section 2.3 of D1.2 [7]. Table 4 also identifies the data which need to be measured for the calculation of the PIs. The PIs are generally measured at application level. Special attention is paid to the PIs related to handover and roaming.
- **Business KPIs** are used to assess the ecosystems from a business perspective and are obtained through quantitative and qualitative analyses carried out in WP5 "Commercialisation, Innovation Management and Standardisation." The business KPIs are summarized in Table 5 and described in more detail in chapter 5 of D1.2 [7].

Table 4: Use case specific technical PIs and data needed to be measured

PI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
User experienced data rate	The number of correctly received bits contained in the service data units per unit of time (bit/s or bps).	Calculated from application logs during trials.

PI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
End-to-end latency	Elapsed time from the moment a data packet is transmitted by the source application to the moment it is received by the destination application instance(s) [26].	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt at the applications, unique message ID. Note: a distinction is made between the communication end-to-end latency , which is measured at the application at transmission and receipt of messages, and the user-perceived end-to-end latency , which includes processing of e.g., video.
Round Trip Time (RTT)	Time it takes for a data packet to be sent to a destination plus the time it takes for an acknowledgment of that packet to be received back at the origin.	Round trip time is an alternative for end-to-end latency if the UE cannot be synchronised. RTT is measured as the time between transmission and response at the same UE, and hence requires automated acknowledgement at the other end.
(Service) reliability	Ratio of messages which is passed successfully (e.g., end-to-end latency within a predefined time limit) between the actors, within the specified range of the service.	Unique Message ID, timestamp of message transmission and receipt at application.
Application Level Handover Success Rate	Applies to scenarios where an active application-level session (e.g., communication between application client at UE/OBU and the Application Server) needs to be transferred from a source to a destination application instance (e.g., located at MEC hosts at the source and destination networks respectively) because of a cross-border mobility event. The KPI describes the ratio of successfully completed application level handovers i.e., where service provisioning is correctly resumed/ continued past the network level handover, from the new application instance [30] within a predefined time limit.	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt at the applications, unique message ID or: connection break time (Qosium). MNC and MCC.
Service Interruption Time	Duration during which the application does not exchange information during handover situations (e.g., end-to-end latency within a predefined limit).	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt; application output (e.g., video recording of handover event) or: connection break time (Qosium). MNC (Mobile Network Code) and MCC (Mobile Country Code).

PI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
Service Startup Time after Handover	the time between the end of handover and when the service is fully operational.	From handover completion to request to Assisted service continuity (ASC) until first message from CAM service received (a request to Assisted Service Continuity enabler developed in WP2 is involved).
Quality of Service	QoS may implies a list of PIs that need to be fulfilled e.g., RTT latency < 10ms AND Reliability > 99.999.	
Positioning accuracy	Positioning accuracy refers to the closeness of a measured location, to the real location of the device at the time of the measurement (as measured with RTK-GNSS).	UE position compared to more accurate method (if available).
RTK interruption time	Interval during which the UE does not have access to the RTK correction signal when crossing the border [4]	UE position logs.
CAM service instantiation time	time needed for instantiating a CAM service in the CAM Services Platform, from the moment the activation command is sent until the acknowledgement that the CAM service is installed [4].	Integration Fabric log.
coverage	percentage of the pilot area which has radio access.	UE position, MCC, MNC.

Table 5: Business KPIs and data needed to determine the KPI

KPI	Definition	Input data
Maturity/TRL	Technological maturity of a technology.	TRL advancement of the 5G ROUTES ecosystems during the field trials.
Obsolescence	The risk that a technology becomes obsolete.	Continuous monitoring of the project innovations through the Innovation Registry tool and interviews with the Innovation Manager and Innovation and Commercialisation Board.
BCR	Benefit-Cost Ratio: the ratio between discounted economic benefits and costs.	BCR value based on tangible inputs (costs/benefits), sensitivity analysis (stakeholder level) and qualitative assessment through interviews and questionnaires (stakeholder level)

KPI	Definition	Input data
Penetration rate	The assessment of how much a product is being sold or used relative to the total estimated market for that product, expressed as a percentage, based on different deployment scenarios.	Penetration rate (PR) (%) = (number of customers ÷ target market) x 100. For 5G-Routes ecosystems we will need to consider the PR of the 5G equipped vehicle (PRV) and the PR of the 5G infrastructure (PRI). So, the rate of usage of 5G technology over CAM is calculated by: PRV*PRI . The input is not expected from the trials but rather from the predictions for the number of customers and the targeted market size, from the thorough market study (T5.1). For the business impact assessment a market penetration of 100% will be considered to the calculations.
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure (infrastructure, vehicles, Hardware/software, etc) required to bring CAM to wide scale deployment.	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
OPEX	Operating Expenses (Human Resources, Insurance, sales, marketing etc.) required for day-to-day operation of a CAM ecosystem.	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
Revenues per year	Revenues produces by the system.	Qualitative assessment through interviews and questionnaires (stakeholder level).
Return on Investment (ROI)	Expected ROI (e.g., on 5G telecom infrastructure, automotive and CAM enabling technologies) from new market opportunities on 5G CAM.	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
Standardisation	The use of a standardized solution.	Interoperability of the 5G Network (low-medium-high). Contribution to related 5G Network and CAM standards (low-medium-high).
Time to market	The time necessary to offer a commercial system.	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
Existence of alternative solutions	The risk that other solutions perform better than the proposed one.	Continuous monitoring of the project innovations through the Innovation Registry tool and interviews with the Innovation Manager and Innovation and Commercialisation Board.
Opportunities	Opportunities to develop a market around a technology or use case.	Thorough market study and SWOT analysis performed in interviews with internal and external stakeholders.

KPI	Definition	Input data
Deployment time	Time to deployment of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems in relation to EC 5G Action Plan [27] and STRIA Roadmap for STRIA Roadmap for Connected and Automated Transport [28].	Deployment Scenarios: Short (2025), Medium (2030), Long (>2030) Relevant trials input: Ecosystem maturity, Technology integration and coverage options (if any) through surveys with the leaders of the two ecosystems.

4.5 Data Collection for Technical Performance Evaluation

The data collected in the project for technical performance evaluation comprises of raw measurements and observations from field trials, and logs exposing the state of the experiments.

To safely manage research data in a broader sense, a Data Management Plan (DMP) has been defined, aiming to make such data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The DMP contains information related to the types of data the project will generate and collect, the standards that will be used to represent the data during the project and how partners might exploit the data resulting from the project. The DMP sets robust management procedures that will protect personal data collected as a result of project activities, as well as client owned data, from unauthorized use or sharing, also supporting GDPR compliance.

Synchronization of the different data sources is critical, especially for measuring latency which is expected to be in the order of milliseconds.

4.5.1 Data Sources

4.5.1.1 Transport layer data

The traffic between different nodes in the network can be monitored using tools as Qosium (section 4.3.2.1), VEDECOM KPI Manager (section 4.3.2.2). Network traffic at the UE can be monitored using e.g., Keysight Nemo. Network traffic can also be analysed using Wireshark.

Keysight Nemo will be used to collect data for the agnostic KPIs related to cross-border handover events (Section 5.3). This data will be collected during the first phase of the trials for the terrestrial use cases for use cases I and II.

Qosium will be used for assessing the KPIs in use cases I (UC1.3) and use case II (UC3.1), VEDECOM KPI for use case II.

KPIs which are measured include UL/DL TCP/UDP throughput, latency between two nodes, packet error rate.

4.5.1.2 Use Case Specific Application Level Data

For measurements at application level, the logging of the data will be integrated with the use case applications at the user equipment and at the CAM services.

Equipment Data

For technical performance evaluation, information will be collected from other 5G nodes, such as infrastructure and IoT sensors connected to the 5G network, end user devices (including consumer devices) and application servers.

Each device will have a unique identifier (stationID), which consists of a prefix assigned to the partner owning the device, e.g., 35831 for VTT, and a number assigned by the partner.

The following data has to be stored for all devices:

- **Messages: message type** (e.g., CAM (Cooperate Awareness Message), CPM...), **timestamp** included in the V2X message (or e.g., in unix epoch of receipt/transmission of message generation), **station ID** of the sender, **size**;
- **Position: latitude, longitude, speed**, heading, positioning method, accuracy, timestamp of correction data;
- Network data of the UE, such as MNC (Mobile Network Code) and MCC (Mobile Country Code);
- Synchronisation statistics, generated e.g., from Chrony, to be able to assess that time synchronisation has worked;
- RTT or ping information (to e.g., MQTT broker), as backup in case of loss of synchronisation.

It is advised to store all data for a UE in the same file to avoid challenges with combining data from different files.

In case the User Equipment or the IoT sensor has only limited processing capabilities, not all the desired information may be possible to be logged. Synchronisation using Network Time Protocol (NTP) or other technologies may not always be possible.

Vehicle Related Data

Road vehicle data will be collected for the CAM use case test cases. The same data as mentioned above for the equipment will be collected: positioning data, speed, sent and received message timing and size, and optionally yaw rate, acceleration (lateral, longitudinal), speed wheel distance, brake status, manual/automated mode.

For the prototype vehicles, which are used in the CAM use cases, vehicle data is collected directly from the vehicle electronics and for use case 5.1 from OBUs installed on the vehicles carried by the vessel.

Vehicle data is classified as personal data. Most of the vehicles which are used for the CAM tests are research vehicles, which are operated by authorized personnel, and data are only logged for the purpose of the tests, hence there are most likely no issues with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). GDPR.

Event data

To be able to analyse the performance of the CAM Services Platform, and the KPIs related to service interruption, the interaction between the User Equipment and the enablers in the CAM Services Platform should be logged. The following data should be logged at the User equipment: timestamp (e.g., UNIX epoch), network and event description (e.g., ASC request).

Some interactions, e.g., the request from the Predictive Resource Allocation enabler (PRAE) to start an instance of the CAM service in the other domain, and the confirmation of instantiation in the other domain, must be logged at the TWP through subscription to the topics of interest.

Test Metadata

For each experiment, metadata related to the experiment will be collected. This data includes factors which may affect the analysis of the results. Among others, the following data will be collected for controlled tests:

- experiment identifier: use case identifier, test case identifier, repetition identifier;

- For each use case, a set of test cases are identified, corresponding to different variations of the use case (e.g., vehicle speed, presence of road users) and/or different variations of the network;
- environmental conditions: temperature, weather conditions (cloudy, sunny, rain, fog...) and road weather (dry, wet, ice, snow...);
- network configuration;
- events influencing the test execution:
 - deviations from the storyboard, e.g., a pedestrian or vehicle deviated from the agreed trajectory;
 - unexpected traffic events, e.g., additional road users or objects on the track;
 - safety events: the safety driver had to take manual control during automated driving.

Overview of Data Collected for the Different Use Cases

Table 6 gives an overview of the devices, on which data will be collected during evaluation.

Table 6: Overview of devices in 5G-ROUTES where data at application level will be logged

Use Case	Vehicle	other devices	servers and enablers
I	Vehicle OBU		V2X broker
II	Vehicle OBU	Traffic light controller, cameras, RSU	V2X broker CAM service
4.1	-	User smart device (phone or tablet)	Real-time game server on K8
4.2	-	Laptop running VR Player	Multicast service on K8.
5.1	OBU	RSU, IoT devices	Backend
5.2	OBU	Camera on OBU	Cloud server

4.5.2 Data Storage Formats

Raw measurements with related parameters, such as timestamps, etc., are stored in plain text format, such as comma separated values (CSV). The raw measurements are pre-processed at the time of data-collection to remove any personally identifiable information, such as IP address, leaving only anonymous and unique machine identifiers along with other parameters related to computations. Logs that contain the history of the state of various processing elements are also stored in plain text format.

The data, which have been used for evaluation, will be uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal, as described in section 4.3.1, and at the end of the project transferred to Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories.

To distinct between the different files, the following naming is suggested:

`<log_item>_<log_stationid>_<experimentID>.<filetype>`

Where:

- **log_item**: Identifies the type of log_item contained in the file. Examples are: "Message", "Position", "VehicleDynamics", "Perception" and "ApplicationEvent";
- **log_stationid**: StationID of the device generating the logging;
- **experimentID**: the ID of the experiment, received from the Tenant Web Portal. If no experiment ID is received, the timestamp in either Unix epoch or YYYYMMDD'T'HHmmss format is used. The same identifier should be used for all files, collected from different devices, and belonging to the same experiment;

- **filetype**: Standard file type of the log file, e.g., “csv”. The first row contains the names of the parameters to be stored.

For each logged row, the following data has to be included:

- **log_timestamp**: timestamp at which the log application logs the item, corresponding to unix epoch time. The timestamp should be the first value on each row.
- **log_stationID**: the log station that has sent or transmitted the data;

4.5.3 Data Quality Requirements

To be useful for evaluation, the quality of the data has to be assured. This includes the following aspects:

- **Timing synchronization**. As the latency PI targets are in the order of 10 ms, the time in the different 5G-nodes must be synchronised to be able to measure latency. A high accuracy is required due to the low expected latencies; hence target should be to have accuracy in the 1 ms range. The following techniques can be used for time synchronisation:
 - The preferred technique is the use of PTP (Precision Time Protocol);
 - GNSS time reference for the 5G nodes. Use of the PPS (Pulse per Second) signal allows for synchronisation with other sensors;
 - NTP (Network Time Protocol) or Chrony. NTP typically provides a precision in the order of a millisecond.
- **Sanity check of all variables**, i.e., that the variables are within the expected range (e.g., locations near the actual site, speeds in normal range).
- **All mandatory data is stored**. Mandatory data for exchanged messages includes:
 - unique reference number for the message, so that a single message can be traced along its delivery path;
 - logging timestamp of the message.
- **The data is logged in the agreed format**. Data are stored in csv files. The different variables are in the agreed units and in the agreed format, e.g., timestamp represented as Unix epoch time, and speeds in km/h.
- **The values of the logged data are within the expected range**, e.g., GNSS-data are not zero.
- **When performing measurements at application level at the UE**, it should be assured that there are no other applications or functions which may affect the timing of the receipt or transmission of the messages.

During border crossing, the service may be disrupted for a time. A set of KPIs has been identified for the measurement of service interruption. During the service interruption period, temporary abnormal values for the metrics such as for metrics such as latency and data rate, can be measured. In addition, the measured values at both sides of the border can be different, due to e.g., different configuration of the networks or longer data transmission paths. The measurements for cross-border tests may have to be split in several parts: connection to network A, handover/service disruption, connection to network B, and the metrics to be calculated for each part separately based on the measurement logs containing these events.

Data regarding the connection to network and the 5G-ROUTES enablers, used by the use case, should be collected to assess the behaviour of the use case on the border and the impact of the enablers of the handover process.

4.5.4 Calculation of Performance Indicators from Measured Values

For each experiment, a set of data is obtained consisting of:

- series of measured values, such as message transmission/receival timestamps, message size, position, (message payload information), network data;
- event data, e.g., device state change, application decisions.

For time series of numerical values, a number of statistical metrics can be obtained, such as:

- median;
- 95% percentile (or any other percentile);
- average;
- minimum, maximum;
- standard deviation;
- confidence interval.

For a test case, the tests will be repeated under the same conditions for improved statistical relevance. The amount of experiments (repetitions) for each test case should preferably be repeated 10 times.

After collection of the data, a quality check is performed, and the different Performance Indicators are calculated for the different experiments. Selected PIs, which are selected as being important for the evaluation of the use case, are then entered as PI in the Tenant Web Portal.

The values of the PIs for different experiments of a specific test case are then compared, to check if they can be combined, or if there is a significant difference caused by e.g., vehicle speed, environmental conditions or the local configuration of the network, or due to an abnormal event during the experiment execution. In case there is a significant difference between the PIs of different experiments, the experiment may be assessed as belonging to a new test case.

The PIs, obtained for the separate experiments, must be aggregated to a PI for the test case. When PIs are calculated from time series, care has to be taken that the calculated aggregated values have a sound mathematical basis. Initially, the aggregated value for the test case is calculated in the Tenant Web as the average of the different experiments.

Composite indicators, as defined in D1.9, are then calculated for the test case and visualised.

4.6 Collection of Data for Business Validation

4.6.1.1 Customer Validation and Solution Alignment Surveys and Interviews

The Customer Validation phase requires a detailed examination of the key personas within each ecosystem and the anticipated benefits they envision from the widespread adoption of the proposed scenario.

This data will primarily be gathered from the stakeholders of the two ecosystems through a structured survey format, supplemented by targeted interviews to clarify specific details. The following Figure 13 illustrates the questionnaires that have been used as the basis to guide the interviews and collect the data required for the Customer Validation process. Specifically, a systematic approach was adopted, focusing on understanding the business context, the personas involved, the existing problems and the expected benefits, by incorporating diverse perspectives and insights.

Business Context and Problem Definition

Background
 Please provide a textual description of the business process and context surrounding the UC.
 What is the general context of the UC? (describe situation in which the UC arises; be specific; focus on the Business/commercial side rather than technical)
 Under what circumstances does the UC arise?
 How often?
 Other information?

Describe the Personas
 Please describe ALL personas who are directly involved in YOUR specific UC;
 Please be as specific and detailed as possible about exactly what each persona does.

Category: Users (e.g. Drivers, vehicle owners, Passengers, Pedestrians,...)

Persona Name	Persona Role

Category: Telecom (i.e. manufacturers, operators)

Persona Name	Persona Role

Category: Transport (i.e. rail, maritime or automotive manufacturers, rail, maritime or automotive operators)

Persona Name	Persona Role

Category: Service providers (i.e. ITS service providers, Network service providers, Infotainment service providers, Consultants/Business innovators)

Persona Name	Persona Role

Category: Others (i.e. Research, Public Authorities, Standardisation Network/Authorities, other (please indicate))

Describe the Problem
 Describe in detail the problems that each persona/stakeholder currently experience (AS-IS today before 5G)

Personas (who exactly?) experience this **problem** (what exactly?) when doing this **task** (when does it occur?) OR
Personas (who exactly?) experience this **problem** (what exactly?) because of this **constraint** or limitation (when does it occur?)

End user Persona	
Problem	
Task / Constraint	
How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)	

Application Provider Persona	
Problem	
Task / Constraint	
How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)	

Other Personas	
Problem	
Task / Constraint	
How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)	

Describe the Expected Benefit
 Describe the benefit that each persona hopes to achieve from the UC (after 5G is implemented).
 Please try to be specific on the benefits that may apply ... Cost? Time? Agility? Safety? Security?

End user personas	
Describe benefit	
Specific benefit	Quantify the potential benefit
Cost reduction?	
Revenue Increase?	
Time saved?	
Faster Time-to-Market?	
Safety?	
Security?	
Accessibility?	
Persona experience?	
Other...	

Application Provider Personas	
Describe benefit	
Specific benefit	Quantify the potential benefit
Cost reduction?	
Revenue Increase?	
Time saved?	
Faster Time-to-Market?	
Safety?	
Security?	
Accessibility?	
Persona experience?	
Other...	

Other Personas	
Describe benefit	
Specific benefit	Quantify the potential benefit
Cost reduction?	
Revenue Increase?	
Time saved?	
Faster Time-to-Market?	
Safety?	
Security?	
Accessibility?	
Persona experience?	
Other...	

Figure 13: Customer Validation Survey used in 5G-ROUTES: Business Context and Problem Definition, Customer segment (persona) definition, Expected Benefits.

Initially, the specific business context surrounding each ecosystem was analysed, emphasising commercial aspects over technical details, as well as the main personas (specific customer segment) directly involved within each case, therefore providing a clear understanding of the business environment. A comprehensive analysis of the current drawbacks and issues within the targeted ecosystem was also undertaken to describe the problems experienced by the stakeholders along with the alternative solutions currently in use. Lastly, the expected benefits from the proposed solution were outlined, to offer clarity on the value proposition of the proposed offerings.

The insights gleaned will be documented and reported in D5.2.

Solution Alignment builds upon the insights gained from Customer Validation, leveraging them to assess the potential products within the project and determine their market fit. It addresses two key questions:

- (i) Which products have the potential to be brought to market?
- (ii) Which partners are best suited to lead the development of the business plan and commercialisation efforts?

In the context of 5G-ROUTES, the goal is to assess the two ecosystems' solutions. A lead commercial partner will be designated for each market service, considering factors such as the anticipated customer journey and the commercial and technical capacity and expertise in each respective field of activity. A structured survey, illustrated in Figure 14, will be applied during interviews with the commercial leader to delve deeper into the exploitation details foreseen by each partner. This process involves a thorough examination of the output intended for commercialisation in each ecosystem to maximise the value proposition for potential customers.

Through the surveys, a clear vision for the benefits to customers will be created by detailing the problems to be addressed through the proposed solutions and how it would be integrated into existing businesses. Additionally, the unique value proposition and the benefits offered will be articulated to further outline the targeted customer segment. The findings from this process will be reported in D5.2.

Commercial Exploitation Potential

Please provide your ideas on the outputs your business hopes to commercialise from 5G-ROUTES. Be as explicit as possible in defining the potential outputs and setting a vision for the offering that your company could create.

What?
<i>Please describe the Product(s) and/or Service(s) that you believe you could commercialise from this project</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>What does the product(s) or service(s) do for a customer? What problem does it address?</i> 2. <i>How would it fit into your current business? Do you already provide a related product/service, or would this be something completely new for your business?</i> 3. <i>How might the product/service be delivered? Is it hardware? Software? Software- As-A-service, A/ Gaming Device? Consultancy/advisory service? Etc. etc.</i>
Who?
<i>Please describe the customer(s) who would pay for the product or service that you envisage</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Can you describe who you believe is the customer(s) for the product/service? (examples: Users (e.g. Drivers, vehicle owners, Passengers, Pedestrians, ..), Telecom (i.e. manufacturers, operators), Transport (i.e. rail, maritime or automotive manufacturers, rail, maritime or automotive operators), Service providers (i.e. ITS service providers, Network service providers, Infotainment service providers, Consultants/Business innovators), Others (i.e. Research, Public Authorities, Standardisation Network/Authorities, other (please indicate))</i> 2. <i>Top 3 specific customer segments who will care the most about your product? And Why?</i>
Why?
<i>Why would customers choose your (future) offering above other approaches? What do you think will make it special?</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>What is special about your offering? What is "game-changing" from other products and/or services?</i> 2. <i>Can you describe the market opportunity for your company? (e.g. we could replace x% of all current products in area-y within 5 years; we could attract 5% of all current users of y within 10 years, etc.).</i>

Figure 14: Solution Alignment Survey used in 5G-ROUTES

4.6.1.2 Workshops

Stakeholder workshops act as a major data collection tool for the implementation of the MAMCA methodology. The aims of those workshops are twofold:

- To identify and weight the business criteria (internal stakeholder rating);
- To rank the value propositions against the weighted criteria and against each other (resulting to max 2 value propositions to be processed in the CBA).

To facilitate the latter, more complex process, stakeholders are presented with the business context (5G ROUTES ecosystems), including a real (or video) demonstration where feasible, to have a better understanding of the business potential. This knowledge will give them the right insight to follow the MAMCA ranking of the proposed value propositions and rate them against the identified business criteria.

One workshop took place for the business criteria identification and rating (Step 3 of MAMCA method depicted in Figure 7), on a horizontal basis (use case independent but relevant to the business potential of 5G as enabler of CAM), and at the next phase, one workshop per each business ecosystem (maritime and terrestrial) that selects the most promising value propositions and the related business criteria where the CBA should focus on (Step 5 of MAMCA method).

4.6.1.3 Interviews

Stakeholder interviews will support the in-depth business analysis and CBA.

After each stakeholder ecosystem is evaluated through the two MAMCA workshops, the interviews plan to assess the clear business interest in the 5G-ROUTES solutions or otherwise a significant role in an emerging business ecosystem. Such interviews will be restricted to 1-2 identified business investor(s)/leader(s) per each 5G-ROUTES defined business ecosystem. This process will be based upon the Delphi² method.

The value propositions discussed in the interviews will be selected based on a role and interest of an interviewee along with the results of the previous data collection tools. A thorough SWOT analysis will be performed during the interview and corrections to the financial and economic models will be taken into consideration.

Finally, the opportunities for exploitation of 5G-ROUTES business values will be discussed and scaled-up, creating new markets beyond the limits of 5G-ROUTES ecosystems.

² <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/delphi-method.asp>

5 Network Key Performance Indicators and Their Data Collection

In deliverable D1.5 [3], the metrics for validating 5G network features, and their test methodologies have been described. These measurements, which were planned to be performed by the MNOs (Mobile Network Operators) involved in the project, were also described in D1.5. The sources of the PI definitions come from NGMN 5G Trial and Testing Initiative Pre-Commercial Network Trials Framework Definition [36], ITU-R M.2410-0 [37][35], 5G PPP Phase II KPI definitions[38], other 5G-PPP projects and 3GPP documents [39].

Following the changes in the consortium, more specifically the departure of the MNOs from the project, the tests were reviewed towards their relevance for the project and the possibility to perform the measurements with tools available to the project partners, like Nemo Keysight.

This chapter will deal with the network KPIs which will be measured for both the terrestrial and the maritime environment. From the Performance Indicators defined in D1.5 [3], the most relevant for the trials, and which can be measured using the Nemo Keysight and transport level tools, like Qosium, are described, both the definition and the measurement method.

5.1 Data rate

5.1.1 Definition

Data rate is the number of bits transmitted through the system per unit of time. There are several data rate KPIs related to the performance of 5G systems. In the 5G-ROUTES project the user experienced data rate and peak data throughput will be addressed. The definitions are based on ITU-R requirements for IMT-2020 [37].

In 5G networks, compared to previous generations, the main enhancement of data rate comes from higher spectral efficiency, utilizing a better MIMO scheme and increased bandwidth from new spectrum assets.

Peak data rate

Peak data rate is the maximum DL/UL data throughput achievable for a single user located at the best location within a cell. Peak data rate is defined for a single mobile station. In a single band, it is related to the peak spectral efficiency in that band. Let W denote the channel bandwidth and SE_p denote the peak spectral efficiency in that band. Then the user peak data rate R_p is given by:

$$R_p = W \times SE_p$$

Peak spectral efficiency and available bandwidth may have different values in different frequency ranges. In case bandwidth is aggregated across multiple bands, the peak data rate will be summed over the bands. Therefore, if bandwidth is aggregated across Q bands, then the total peak data rate is

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^Q W_i \times SE_{p_i}$$

where W_i and SE_{p_i} ($i = 1, \dots, Q$) are the component bandwidths and spectral efficiencies respectively.

This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the eMBB usage scenario.

From the ITU requirement report [35], we find the minimum requirements for peak data rate as follows:

- downlink peak data rate is 20 Gbit/s;
- uplink peak data rate is 10 Gbit/s.

Those numbers could only be achieved by using much larger bandwidth of spectrum which is available in the 26 GHz frequency band. Also, a massive MIMO solution would have to be used for which today there are no available end user devices.

In the terrestrial solution, for 5G-ROUTES use cases, 100 MHz of 3.5 GHz TDD spectrum, with 4 MIMO layers will be used. This provides us the theoretical peak maximums of up to 1.5Gbps for DL and 200Mbps for UL. However, in reality, only 600-900 Mbps for DL and 60-120 Mbps for UL, depending on the distance, is achievable.

In this project, peak data rate is not as important KPI as user experienced data rate, however it gives us a good starting point when evaluating the overall user experience.

User Experienced Data Rate

User experienced data rate is defined as the number of correctly received bits, i.e. the number of bits contained in the service data units delivered to Layer 3, over a certain period of time.

5.1.2 Measurement

5.1.2.1 Peak data rate

The peak data rates in UL and DL directions are measured with TCP traffic generated by an IPERF3 traffic generator. The DL throughput is measured with Keysight Nemo using five parallel IPERF3 streams. UL and DL throughputs are measured in multiple 5G stack layers including application, Packet Data Conversion Protocol (PDCP), Physical Downlink / Uplink Shared Channel (PDSCH / PUSCH). In addition, performance parameters such as Modulation and Coding Scheme MCS index, modulation, DL Block Error Rate (BLER), UL retransmission rate, MIMO mode and antenna rank are recorded.

5.1.2.2 User experienced data rate

The user experienced UL and DL data rates are recorded using 15 Mbps UDP traffic generated with IPERF3 traffic generator and/or with 15 Mbps TCP UL/DL video. The same parameters as in case of peak data rates are measured. The measurements are done in LOS and NLOS conditions.

5.2 Mobility

5.2.1 Definition

Mobility is the maximum mobile terminal movement speed at which a defined QoE can be achieved (in km/h).

The following classes of mobility are defined:

- Stationary: 0 km/h;
- Pedestrian: 0 km/h to 10 km/h;
- Vehicular: 10 km/h to 120 km/h;
- High-speed vehicular: 120 km/h to 500 km/h.

In the 5G-ROUTES project we are mainly looking into the vehicular class, as the speed limits on the roads in the Valga/Valka test area are up to 70 km/h.

5.2.2 Measurement

5.2.2.1 Intra cell mobility

This section considers testing the intra-cell mobility for different UE speeds and angles to transmission point. In addition, performance, throughput, packet loss in different mobility scenarios and for different services should be verified. We give different testing scenarios for maximum angle mobility and maximum doppler mobility.

Maximum angle mobility

Intra-cell mobility with different angles to transmission point is considered in this section. This section covers mobility without RRC, so some aspects of beam tracking are also included.

Test setup

The test is performed in the test environment along the track followed by the vehicles (for terrestrial, the E264 road crossing the border in Valga-Valka, for maritime, the fairway from Vuosaari towards Muuga), ferry allowed speed. For terrestrial, two vehicle speeds are considered: 15 and 60 km/h.

Test procedure

1. The 5G NR Base Station(s) is/are powered on and configured with related parameters.
2. All the UEs are under 5G NR cell coverage.
3. UEs are powered on and complete initialization process.
4. UEs are successfully attached to the 5G network and are able to upload/download data.
5. All UEs start uploading/downloading data (e.g. use of Iperf3 TCP IP).
6. UEs should start movement along the road. Speed of the car should stay the same during the test.
7. Continuously monitor DL/UL throughput, latency (RTT).
8. The scenario shall be repeated with different speeds, as mentioned above.

Success criteria

- the service shall continue without interruption;
- DL/UL throughput, user plane latency and packet loss should be observed along the route;
- signal strength variations should also be tracked based on Beam ID.

From the NGMN 5G whitepaper [40] 50 Mbps DL and 25 Mbps UL throughput is expected on minimum for the mobile car.

5.3 Handover time

5.3.1 Definition

Handover time is the brief interruption time in which a mobile terminal cannot transmit or receive data when a mobile terminal is moving from a source cell to a target cell. In D1.5 testing methodologies are described for several different cases of handover like Intra-gNB and Inter-gNB. The most important scenario for cross-border focus is Inter PLMN handover, where the mobile terminal is moving from an MNO to another MNO.

Handover has three main phases: preparation, execution and completion. The handover procedure starts with an event at the UE generating a measurement report to the source gNB. This measurement report results in a handover request from the gNB to the target gNB. For intra-network handover, the RRC connection

reconfiguration message acts as a handover command, starting the execution phase. At that moment, the user-plane traffic interrupts, and the source gNB forwards the traffic to the target gNB, which buffers the packets. The handover ends after the UE sends a handover confirm (RRC Configuration complete) message to the target gNB and the UE receives the first data packet from the target gNB.

Figure 15: Handover preparation time and mobility interruption time during handover between 5G networks

Based on this process, the following KPIs are defined at control level:

- **Handover preparation time:** time between the measurement report by the UE, triggering the handover, until the start of handover execution (RRC Connection Reconfiguration) event. For intra-network handover this causes only minimal delay, but in case of roaming there may be considerable delays, and during this time the performance of the network may be poor.
- **Mobility Interruption Time:** The time duration during which a user terminal cannot exchange user plane Packets with any base station (or other user terminal) during transitions. This is defined as the time difference between RRC Connection Reconfiguration and New Data Receive messages.

5.4 Latency

5.4.1 Definition

User plane latency is the contribution of the radio network to the time from when the source sends a packet until the destination receives it. It is defined as the one-way time it takes to successfully deliver an application layer packet/message from the radio protocol layer 2/3 SDU ingress point to the radio protocol layer 2/3 SDU egress point of the radio interface in either uplink or downlink in the network for a given service in unloaded conditions, assuming the mobile station is in the active state [37].

This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the eMBB and URLLC usage scenarios.

The minimum requirements for user plane latency are: 4 ms for eMBB and 1 ms for URLLC, assuming unloaded conditions (i.e. a single user) for small IP packets (e.g. 0-byte payload + IP header), for both downlink and uplink. These can be, however, hard to be reached with current state of NR evolution and for 5G-ROUTES user plane latency < 10 ms would be satisfactory.

Both UL and DL latency are measured. For URLLC, the target for user plane latency should be 0.5 ms for UL, and 0.5 ms for DL. Furthermore, if possible, the latency should also be low enough to support the use of the next generation access technologies as a wireless transport technology that can be used within the next generation access architecture. For eMBB, the target for user plane latency should be 4 ms for UL, and 4ms for DL [41].

5.4.1.1 Control plane latency

Control plane latency refers to the transition time from a most “battery efficient” state (e.g. Idle state) to the start of continuous data transfer (e.g. Active state). However, the measurement tools (Keysight Nemo) is only able to perform measurements in the active state, and hence the control plan latency cannot be measured.

5.4.2 Measurement

Latency is measured using ping and UDP traffic. The one-way latency in UL and DL directions is measured with Qosium and the round-trip time (RTT) with Nemo. The latency is measured using Ping and UDP traffic. The one-way delay requires accurate time synchronization using PTP between a mobile terminal and an application server. For two-way latency, the UL and DL latencies measured by Qosium are summed.

5.5 Jitter

5.5.1 Definition

Jitter typically refers to the deviation of the periodicity of a signal. It quantifies the fluctuation in delay as packets are being transferred across a network. This effect can be experienced as a disruption in the normal sequence of sending data packets, which eventually may reflect even to network congestion and packet loss. Packet jitter is expressed as an average of the deviation from the network mean delay and is an important QoS factor in the assessment of network performance. Jitter can degrade the user experience and the QoS. There are two types of jitter: deterministic and random jitter. Deterministic jitter is systematic either periodical or data dependent. Deterministic jitter is bounded and specified as a peak-to-peak value. Random jitter is unbounded and commonly specified by the standard deviation. Random jitter is uncorrelated and has unpredictable behaviour.

5.5.2 Measurement

Deterministic jitter is assessed as Packet Delay Variation (PDV). Jitter is calculated for the data collected when measuring latency. For assessing jitter, we choose the maximum of UL and DL jitter values measured by Qosium.

5.6 Quality of Service

Following the definition of Quality of Service in Table 4, this indicator is calculated according to the fulfilment of selected indicators. The Quality of Service is calculated from the amount of time, that all PIs are higher than predefined threshold values.

5.7 Other performance indicators

The indicators in the previous sections were selected due to their possibility to be measured with Nemo and Qosium. The original KPIs were defined by the MNOs, but they are not anymore in the 5G-ROUTES consortium. The following Performance Indicators were not selected for measurement:

- connection density: the measurement requires a high amount of UEs;
- reliability: the test scenarios require to switch base stations on and off, which is a challenging operation;
- position accuracy: meant for the accuracy of network positioning and is the accuracy is compared to a more accurate method, like GNSS. GNSS RTK will be used for the automated driving related functionalities in 5G-ROUTES;
- coverage: all measurements will be performed on a fixed test route.

6 Test Plan

This chapter discusses test plan issues at a general level. The test plan will be generated before the start of the test session, where information for the evaluation is collected in WP4. The test cases are described in more detail in D4.1 [11]. The test plan has two purposes:

- it is a tool to guarantee the success of the trials, i.e., that the trials are performed without problems, and that the tests generate high quality data for evaluation;
- it is a reference document for external evaluators, to explain what is happening, including all aspects which may have an impact on the interpretation of the result, e.g., potential bias if the environment is not completely corresponding to a real traffic environment.

The test plan must address the following issues:

- description of the use case to be tested;
- overview of the test cases to be performed;
- planning of the test events;
- organisation of the test events.

6.1 Use Case Description and Test Cases

For the evaluation, a clear description of the use case is required. This description can be used to describe to the stakeholders, test users, evaluation team and other actors how the use case is performed, and what the role of each actor and participant in the use case is.

The test plan should also include an extensive list of all the test cases which are planned to be tested, i.e., the variations in network configuration, road users and test parameters.

Elements of the use case description are:

- description of the actors involved in the test and their roles;
- storyboard, describing the consecutive phases of the use cases (and potential alternatives). Graphs with e.g., the position and movements of all actors are beneficial;
- description of the information flow between the different components, including sequence diagram. Description of the messages which are exchanged, including the standards or specification in use. Description of the security solution in place (e.g., TLS), including details on how to receive the required certificates;
- description of the network infrastructure, vehicles and other sensors and devices used in the test. Description of the potential different configurations of the communication network. Description of the 5G-ROUTES enablers which are implemented in the network.

Test cases

For the use cases, different test cases are described in D4.1 [11]. In this phase, the test cases will be detailed. This includes:

- description of the test route;
- description of the test cases and the potential variations:
 - description of network variations (e.g. direction of the route, used SIM for the UEs);
 - determining the parameters for performing the tests, e.g., target vehicle speed and initial vehicle distance;

- determination of the number of experiments (repetitions) or sample size, to guarantee statistical relevant results. For technical performance, each scenario should ideally be repeated 10 times under identical circumstances in order to get statistical relevant results;

6.2 Test Preparation

During this period, after having determined the test cases to be tested, the following categories must be addressed:

- administrative and ethical issues: assuring that all permits are in place, and ethical issues are addressed;
- system preparation: assuring that all tools are in place for data collection;
- test logistics.

6.2.1 Administrative and Ethical Issues

This section deals with administrative issues to be handled well in advance, such as assuring that all permits are in place, and with ethical issues, related to ensuring the safety of all test participants and the privacy of involved road and test users.

The following issues have to be addressed:

- applying for and acquiring the permits needed for performing out the tests at the test site;
 - for testing of automated driving on public roads, specific registration procedures are needed. If the roads are closed for other traffic, these registration procedures are not needed. Hence, in order to perform automated driving tests, the roads must be closed for other public traffic, or the tests have to be performed at a closed site;
 - in case the tests are performed on public roads, special provisions may be required by local or national authorities to ensure the safety of all road users. This may include specific road (work) permits and putting traffic signs or trailers in place. Closing roads may also lead to additional requirements such as guidance for deviation roads and informing drivers and public;
 - in case radio equipment is installed, the required radio permits have to be received from the respective authorities. Care should be taken that radio emissions remain below the agreed thresholds.
- ensuring the safety of test participant and all road users:
 - in case the use case addresses safety critical traffic situations, it must be ensured that no actual damage to persons or vehicles will occur. Automated vehicles require a safety driver which can take control at each moment and override the automated actions. It also may require limiting the speed of the manoeuvre, so that the safety driver has sufficient time to react;
 - in case tests are performed on public road: the actions, needed to inform the public about the test have to be discussed with local authorities. If a road or a section of the road is temporary close, safety equipment to guide the public, such as road guiding trailers, may have to be put in place. Dependent on local regulations, persons, who have the required permits, must be hired to guide traffic.
- privacy related issues: assuring that all GDPR issues are addressed, including assessment whether a DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment) is needed.
- potential labour related issues, e.g., in case tests are performed at night.

6.2.2 System Preparation

The use cases to be demonstrated must be prepared for the trials. The use case developers have to assure that all data collection measures are in place, and that data of high quality can be collected. This includes e.g., assuring that, if needed, RTK correction data is available.

The use cases may require detailed information on the road network and/or telecommunication network topology. It has to be assured that the use cases have the required information.

6.2.3 Logistic Issues

Organising CAM tests is a resource intensive task, especially if it involves different vehicles of different partners and different telecom providers, and several use cases may be tested in parallel. Hence, during the same testing period, several use cases will have to work together, and the different testing activities must be coordinated, especially if different use cases have different demands regarding the 5G network configuration. Tests take generally several days, involving at least one preparation day to assure that everything is working. Provisions have to be taken that the persons participating in the tests can work efficiently and safely. The following aspects have to be addressed:

- issues related to the test site/facility:
 - contact persons at site/facility, which are responsible for, respectively, the interaction between researchers and facility managers/local authorities and the interaction between the researchers and on-site technicians. Contact persons for technical issues, e.g., related to 5G-networks or SIM cards. This is also including briefing of the researchers.
 - access to the test site/facilities:
 - timing: during which days and time of the day the test facilities are available;
 - security related issues: are access permits required?, is free movement within the test site facility allowed?, etc.;
 - visitors to the tests: can visitors (e.g., reviewers, local authorities, dissemination public) be invited to the tests, and which specific procedures for access control to the facility?
 - services needed for the test:
 - access to electric power, also for charging electric vehicles,
 - installation of devices and systems, which may have permanent impact on the facility, has to be agreed with the facility contact person. If the devices or systems are installed for the whole test period, agreements have to be made with the facility contact person for e.g. procedures to restart or reboot the system in case of failures.
 - local services:
 - control room or space (e.g., heated tent), which can be used by the researchers for coordination of the test activities and for e.g., solving software problems or verifying test results. Researchers should not be forced to work outside in the cold, heat or rain...
 - potentially room which can be used for dissemination: in case there are external experts (e.g., reviewers, invited authorities...) coming to see the trials, there should be a possibility for giving short presentations;
 - in case the test involves external test users, location where briefing and interviews will take place;
 - availability of catering;
 - parking and storage related issues: there should be a location where test equipment can be securely stored in between testing days.

- in case the facility shared with other actors (either internally in the project – with other use cases, or externally to the project), the interaction between the different actors should be clear.
- schedule:
 - time should be foreseen for: setting up equipment and pre-test; time for performing tests; time for dismantling and debriefing. In case different use cases are being tested in the same period in the same location, a more detailed timing of testing of the different use cases is needed.
 - for maritime use cases
 - the interaction between use case testing and the movement of ferry should be clear, e.g., if there any specific processes at the terminals (i.e., in between the ferry is at the end destination and returns to the start).
 - in case multiple boats/vessels are involved, the timing and potential movement of the vessels should be agreed.

7 Use Case Specific Aspects

7.1 Terrestrial Ecosystem

7.1.1 I. See-Through Platooning

1. Use case

The objective of the use is to demonstrate how CAM services, deployed in the available points of presence by the CAM Services Platform, which is developed in 5G-ROUTES, can be used to support drivers when moving across borders. Demonstrated support functions are platooning for automated vehicles supported by see-through video transmission as well as remote support to the drivers.

In the platooning sub use-case (UC1.1), the objective is to implement a system for automated vehicles to dynamically form a platoon with harmonized speeds, following a piloting vehicle. By using a combination of sensors and communication, the aim is to reduce inter-vehicular distances to a safe minimum while also supporting border crossing and providing a camera-based fallback mechanism.

During the platoon, vehicles can perform automated lane change manoeuvres (UC1.2), while also taking into account the intentions of other vehicles. By using a combination of sensors and communication, movements of the vehicles are coordinated in a way that reduces unnecessary changes in speed and keeps the drivers safe, while also supporting border crossing scenarios.

The see-through capability (UC1.3) gives the (safety) driver of a vehicle in a platoon a view of the traffic situation in front of the leading vehicle. The main objective of this sub-use case is to provide enhanced visibility of road awareness during platooning and for safe automated manoeuvres. The objective is to support the driver to make decisions when there is a need to leave the platoon.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

The main cross-border issue is to guarantee service continuity and low latency V2X message transmission for the entire duration of the platoon while the vehicles are crossing the border, as well as to provide continuous video transmission between the vehicle in front and the following vehicles.

The use case makes use of the video proxy CAM service for transmission of the video, which is integrated with the CAM Services Platform. The solution also makes use of the platoon management service, which is deployed on the cloud. The CAM services follow the vehicles when crossing the border.

The use of slicing is beneficial in guaranteeing low latency for the V2X messages needed for the execution of the use case (e.g., vehicle odometry, status information) and for the distribution of the video.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity for the service, respectively.
- The 5G-ROUTES enablers allow to instantiate the virtualise CAM services in the visiting network in time to guarantee seamless service continuity (Local Breakout configuration).
- Slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and throughput.
- High positioning accuracy for supporting automated driving is available at both sides of the border.

- Different live video sources streamed on the same network do not collide or overload the network bandwidth capacity.

4. Use case scenarios

The following evaluation tests are planned:

- Preliminary trials: transmission of video and of V2X messages between 2 UEs. The second UE is either static or in the same vehicle.
- Execution of the use case scenario for 2 crossing the border:
 - platoon consisting of 2 crossing the border (UC1.1);
 - platoon of 2 vehicles performing lane change manoeuvre in the border area (UC1.2);
 - video transmission between 2 vehicles following each other across the border (UC1.3);
 - demonstration of use case scenario with 2 or 3 vehicles and video transmission.

The use of slicing will be evaluated, with one slice for the V2X traffic and one slice for the video transfer.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

- EDI: develop cooperative driving-related applications and services (UC1.1, UC1.2), supply two electric vehicles (equipped with LIDAR, radar, camera, GNSS-RTK, 5G communication system, drive-by-wire system and on-board computer) capable of automated driving, that can also host VTT's video streaming application if needed.
- VTT: responsible for video streaming application development (UC1.3), and for the OBU which takes care of video transmission, streaming and reception (1 OBU with camera, 1 OBU with display).
- TTU and Ericsson: provide network infrastructure.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials for platooning (UC1.1 and UC1.2) are mainly performed on the Biķernieki racetrack, where a simulated border-crossing environment is provided. Small-scale tests are also done in EDI premises, where a small intersection and roads with lane-markings are available in addition to a commercial 5G network.

Lab trials for the video transmission (UC1.3) are performed in Finland in both VTT's 5GTN network in Otaniemi, and in the commercial 5G networks. Additional lab trials are performed in conjunction with CTTC lab to test the integration of UC1.3 with the required enablers of the CAM Services Platform.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

For testing automated driving: Closed road, controllable environment.

8. Location for field trials

E264 motorway between Estonia and Latvia borders. In specific, crossing the cities of Valka and Valga.

Automated driving cannot be performed on public roads, following discussions with the Latvian road operator. Automated driving tests will be performed in Biķernieki.

9. Logging of data and logging process

For platooning and lane change (UC1.1, UC1.2): Logging utilizing ROS based ecosystem, i.e., using rosbag files with synchronized data in addition to Wireshark for network measurements.

For video transmission, data will be collected from the OBUs (which will be installed in EDI vehicles) and from VTT vehicle, and from the video proxy, using Qosium.

Chrony or PTP (Precision Time Protocol) is used to synchronize applications.

The data, collected during trial experiments, will be exported to the Tenant Web tools using the provided API.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

The trials do not include end-user involvement.

7.1.2 II. Sharing Perception and Road Hazard at the Border for Connected and Automated Driving

1. Use case

This use case consists of different functionalities, which involve CAM services which are disseminating data packets towards road users (vehicles, roadworkers...) through the V2X Message Routing enabler to ensure safety and continuity of traffic related information during border crossing. A common requirement is hence that the service continuity has to be assured when crossing borders to maintain a high level of availability in the automated driving functionalities by ensuring that a connected and automated vehicle (CAV) can quickly respond to any unlikely event. As vehicles are driving in mixed conditions, i.e., where vehicles from both sides of the countries are sharing the same driving environment, similar information must be disseminated on both sides.

The use case consists of different the following services:

- 1) **Sensor information sharing for situational awareness** (UC3.1).
- 2) **Infrastructure assisted advanced driving** (based on UC2.1).
- 3) **Collision warning with mobile roadwork operation** (based on UC3.3).

In the **Infrastructure assisted advanced driving** service, 5G networks and road infrastructure technologies are used to improve road users' safety and traffic efficiency in a cross-border environment. Based on ETSI specifications, the periodic broadcast of CPM, CAM, SPATEM, MAPEM messages supports CAVs while driving across the border. The service created through the messages exchange consider the attributes of vehicles, road infrastructure and detected objects.

In the **sensor information sharing** service, processed sensor data is exchanged among vehicles, Road Site Units (RSU), road user UEs and V2X application servers, in order to achieve cooperative situation awareness. Vehicles use their own sensors (e.g., HD camera, LIDAR), and sensor information from other vehicles, to perceive the environment (e.g., come up with 3D model of world around it) and safely performs automated manoeuvres.

In **collision warning with mobile roadwork operation**, safety related information where roadwork agents are in intervention, e.g., for maintenance of the road, is shared. In such condition, a vehicle from a road operator is slowly moving to delimit the roadwork area and warn other users of the dangerous situations. Connected

and automated vehicles approaching from the other side of the border need to be informed and continuously updated as the situation changes.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

The different use cases have the following common challenges:

- The services offered to the vehicle users (mobile roadwork warning, infrastructure perception) should be available on both sides of the border thanks to the V2X Message Broker and accessible when crossing the border without disruption.
- The use cases using CAM services (e.g., mobile roadwork warning, infrastructure perception), should be able to disseminate information to both sides of the border.
- Slicing allows to reserve resources for V2X services, guaranteeing low latency for time critical functionalities, also when crossing borders.
- Availability of 5G positioning enhancing at both sides of the border, assuring sufficiently good accuracy for automated driving.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service.
- Slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and reliability for different types of user equipment (vehicle OBUs, road agent devices, roadside infrastructure router).
- High positioning accuracy for supporting automated driving is available at both sides of the borders.

4. Use case scenarios

The following trials are planned:

- Preliminary trials: transmission of V2X messages between 2 UEs.
- Second set of trials: The objective of this scenario is to assess the performance of 5G and the CAM Services Platform for informing vehicles on safety critical situations and to assist automated driven vehicles.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

Partners and Roles

- SWARCO: main responsible for the Infrastructure-assisted advanced driving service, and will provide the applications.
- VTT is responsible for application development for sensor sharing service, and the OBUs for sensor sharing (1 OBU with camera and LIDAR). VTT will provide a vehicle for testing.
- VEDECOM: Supply vehicles equipped with on-board units and develop roadwork warning of cooperative and automated driving service.
- CERTH: Supply 5G devices and C-ITS applications which can be installed in vehicles (e.g., CAV or road operator vehicle). One portable device can be carried by a roadworker or easily installed in a test vehicle.
- ERICSSON: 5G Infrastructure provider and developer of CAM infrastructure.

- TTU: CAM infrastructure developer.
- Cities: providing the required infrastructure and authorizations for the intelligent infrastructure.

Infrastructure for Valka-Valga intersections:

- 2 Controllers SWARCO Tech;
- 6 Combia traffic lights;
- 10 Beamer devices;
- 2 Roadside Units;
- 4 cameras (i.e., 2 in each intersection);
- 2 Swarm analytic devices with AI capabilities;
- 2 Routers 5G/4G;
- Tablet or a smartphone.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials take place near the facilities of the use case developers: for roadworks warning in Versailles, for perception sharing in Tampere.

Tests for the infrastructure-assisted advanced driving are performed in TTU 5G Testbeds (Tallinn).

Additional lab trials may be performed in conjunction with CTTC lab to test the integration of the virtualised CAM Service Backend of these use cases with the required enablers of the CAM Services Platform

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

5G network to enable the service continuity considering the cross-border scenario.

Cities/Road authorities:

- contacts;
- authorization procedures and guidelines;
- installation activities authorization;
- the configuration of the actual traffic light plan or an updated plan.

Documentation required:

- signal timing sheet;
- intersection electrical drawings;
- installation policies and procedures (according to local authorities).

Roads with accident prone areas (e.g., blind spots, intersections) are expected to highlight the potential benefits of use case services.

When performing automated driving manoeuvres, the roads should be closed for other traffic.

8. Location for field trials

E264 motorway between Estonia and Latvia borders. In specific, crossing the cities of Valka and Valga.

9. Logging of data and logging process

Data will be collected from the OBUs and from the vehicles from VTT and VEDECOM and from the CERTH devices, and from the V2X Message Routing enabler, according to the formats described in D2.7. Data of the intelligent infrastructure will be logged.

Chrony or PTP is used to synchronise clocks between different devices.

The data collected during trial test runs experiments will be exported to the Tenant Web tools using the provided API.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

The main stakeholders are the project partners, the city/road authorities and the road users.

7.1.3 UC4.1 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming on the Go

1. Use case

The main objective of the use case is to allow groups of users to play Augmented Reality (AR) video games while on-route, and to provide a fluid and identical gaming session status to all participants without the need to apply dead reckoning techniques that always lend to unfair game situations for users with higher latency connections.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

Guarantee low-latency data transmission and service continuity even when users are crossing the border. The solution uses a server placed in a point of presence in the edge to deploy the game server to ensure low latency communication and ensure dissemination of messages. When the players are approaching the border the game service is duplicated in the edge of the visiting country and synchronised with the service running in the first country.

The use of slicing is beneficial in guaranteeing low latency data transmission, needed for real-time game update, avoid lag and user synchronization.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service, respectively;
- Real-time game service can be successfully deployed, instantiated and synchronised on the visiting country on edge servers;
- Gaming session data can be exchanged between the servers in an interoperable way;
- The end-to-end latency is within the target;
- Slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and reliability for smart devices.

4. Use case scenarios

The following field trials are planned:

- First set of trials: transmission of gaming data between game server and a single UE (smart phone or tablet) crossing the border.
- Second set of trials:
 - Multi-user gaming for users in vehicles crossing the border (for terrestrial).
 - Multi-user gaming for users on a ferry.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

PARTNERS INVOLVED:

- BRAINSTORM: Leader of the use case. Provides collaborative gaming application and related containerized gaming server;
- ATOS: Validate the use cases in a cross-border multi-operator orchestration environment;
- TTU, Ericsson: provide network environment.

EQUIPMENT:

- **Game servers:** deployed on edge computer near the base stations, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and finally updating all remote devices accordingly.
- **User smart devices:** Android smart phone or tablet will display the last game update from the game server. 5G infrastructure compatible.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trial's location : CTTC – Barcelona. In addition to those tests explained above, CTTC lab will also support trials related to the integration of UC4.1 with the required enablers of CAM Services Platform.

The tests will be focused on the application compatibility and evaluating the 5G network capabilities before the field trials, specifically measure the network latency and how it affects the user QoE.

The data will be captured by the mobile device in order to check the network expected performance.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- Edge node servers on the base stations to assure low latency;
- At least 5 minutes route duration for optimal testing.

8. Location for field trials

- Terrestrial tests: Estonia/Latvia border in Valga;
- Maritime tests: ferry between Tallinn-Helsinki.

9. Logging of data and logging process

Data logged by the smartphones:

- Timestamp for each interaction with the game server;

- Clients KPIs (Full-loop latency, Jitter, Messages in per second, Data in throughput, Data out throughput, Output message size, Input message size) logs.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

Stakeholders:

- Technological institute for children’s products & leisure (AIJU) – technological centre specialized in physical toys and interactive play experiences.

User involvement:

- Gaming application will be analyzed and tested by the above mentioned Institution : as it is not possible to get personnel from AIJU in the lab and to the field trial, the results will be presented to them in the way of documentation, images, and videos, in order to provide them with the necessary information for the analysis of the results and the completion of the corresponding questionnaires.

7.1.4 UC4.2 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move

1. Use case

The main objective of the use case is to allow reduced groups of individuals to participate on remote master class experiences through 5G connection, on-route, and fully immersive through head mounted display devices. The use case will provide the required means for the presenter to be stereoscopically streamed and inserted in real or virtual scenarios including immersive graphic elements to improve presentations.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

Guarantee high-resolution video transmission and service continuity even when users are crossing the border. The solution uses an edge to deploy a CAM service involving a video server in order to redistribute video to all the connected clients from one stream and ensure connection on both sides of the border.

The use of slicing is beneficial in guaranteeing high bandwidth, needed for real-time game video reception and user synchronization.

For correct cross-border functionality, positioning is needed at both sides of the border.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service;
- Real-time multicast video server can be deployed and used successfully on an edge server;
- The 5G-ROUTES enablers allow the multicast service relocation to guarantee seamless service delivery for multiple clients across borders;
- User’s information can be exchanged within the servers in an interoperable way, also across borders;
- slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to bandwidth and reliability.

4. Use case scenarios

The following field trials are planned:

- First set of trials: verification of VR content streaming continuity for one UEs (streaming laptop) and receiving HMD in cross-border environment.
- Second set of trials: Multi-user content consumption continuity for users moving in vehicles across the border.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

PARTNERS INVOLVED:

- BRAINSTORM: Leader of the use case. Provides: content capture and streaming stage, containerized video proxy solution and the VR Player application;
- ATOS, CTTC: Validate the use cases in a cross-border multi-operator orchestration environment;
- TTU and ERICSSON: 5G network infrastructure.

EQUIPMENT:

- **Streaming server:** as the use case requires a real time video input for the testing, a streaming server will be placed near the 5G infrastructure providing the continuous and “live” required video input. In case the 5G network infrastructure does not allow external connections for the tests, the capture and streaming server will be deployed inside the 5G network employing a Nvidia Jetson Nano.
- **Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs):** for showing the virtual scene with the integrated presenter to the users, including head tracking to allow the user immersivity on the scene.
- **High end laptops:** as the actual HMDs do not have the performance neither the connectivity needed for the trials, the rendering will be done externally on laptops, to which the HMD will be connected directly.
- **Smartphones:** In order to provide the laptops, the 5G required connectivity needed for the trials, the mobile devices from the UC 4.1 will be used as modem between the laptops and 5G network.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials location: CTTC – Barcelona. In addition to those tests explained above, CTTC lab will also support trials related to the integration of UC4.2 with the required enablers of CAM Services Platform.

The tests will be focused on the application compatibility and the evaluation of the 5G network capabilities before the field trials, specifically on measuring the network throughput and how it affects the user QoE.

The data will be captured by the laptops in order to check the network expected performance.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- At least 5 minutes route duration for optimal testing;
- recommended 220V power supply in the trial vehicle (car / ferry).

8. Location for field trials

- terrestrial tests: Estonia/Latvia border in Valga;

- maritime tests: Ferry between Tallin-Helsinki.

9. Logging of data and logging process

Data logged by the laptops:

- timestamp for each communication;
- VR client KPIs (Stream resolution, frame rate, bitrate);
- data packet size.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

Stakeholders:

- Pompeu Fabra University (UPF)
- Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)

User involvement:

- Pompeu Fabra University (UPF)
- Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)

As it not possible to get personnel from UPF and NTNU in the lab and field trials, the results will be presented to them in the way of documentation, images, and videos in order to provide them with the necessary information for the analysis of the results and the completion of the corresponding questionnaires.

7.2 Maritime Ecosystem

7.2.1 UC5.1 Connected Logistics

1. Use case

Connected logistics use case focuses on how to provide seamless connection for onboard devices and how this connectivity can be utilised for end user solutions and devices. Connected logistics covers two test themes: 1) vehicle-to-backend system connectivity and 2) cybersecurity health reporting.

Theme 1 covers continuous connectivity between Transport Management Systems (TMS) and critical onboard systems, such as vehicle and/or driver health status and remote monitoring for cargo data for critical and secured transportations (CST). CST basic requirement is uninterrupted situational awareness data, which implies that transportation needs to be monitored continuously via remote control tower with video stream and other security sensors to ensure continuous shipment integrity

Theme 2 utilizes new 5G capabilities and onboard device, which can be used to track and monitor positioning metadata and deviations appearing therein. Such analysis can give information about cybersecurity threats and GNSS spoofing.

Figure 16.: Use case 5.1 illustration (source Vediafi)

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

The use case focuses on maritime transportation that operates between Finland and Estonia. In addition, the case highlights the maritime environment where the communication network quality and coverage are not as good as on the land area, e.g., in the cities or main roads. In this use case, trials focus on the solution on how to enable continuous and high-quality connection in this maritime transport corridor. The solution will cover combination of 5G and multi-hop solutions and satellite connection.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

In status quo, ferry operators have 4G based solutions available and they offer free Wi-Fi for their passengers. For cargo customers, operators do not have specified communication services. The hypothesis for trials is that 5G-ROUTES will provide new and better communication solutions, which provide better quality and enable new services for customers. The hypothesis is also that the new solutions are economically sustainable.

4. Use case scenarios

In UC 5.1. trials the QoS of the 5G onshore multi-hop solution and satellite link will be analysed while crossing the Gulf of Finland, is tested. Focus of the trials is connectivity and capacity of available connections.

Use Case 5.1. aim is to test continuous connection during the ferry trip. The UC utilises on board devices, where vehicle is equipped with OBU and linked RTK-device, IoT sensors and one camera. RTK device is utilised to enable RTK metadata monitor, which further is used to analyse GNSS status information. Video camera and temperature sensor monitors vehicle status during the transportation. The OBU is connected to the ferry communication infrastructure, and it shares location, temperature and time data to backend systems via the 5G-ROUTES communication infrastructure. This data is used to analyse the QoS of connectivity. Aim of the tests is to monitor and measure the quality of service during the ferry trip, with various connectivity setups.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

- Vediafi: connectivity testing/RTK metadata testing/ and use case lead;
- Eckerö Line: Vediafi subcontractor, provides one ferry as test platform;
- Digita: communication devices and network provider on ferry;
- Cumucore: 5G Core;
- Arctia Ltd: second test vessel for field trials;
- Airbus: satellite communication for ferry;
- Brainstorm: link to passenger transport trials and lead of passenger use case 4.1;
- VTT: testing framework and field test support, link between logistics and V2X trials + support to WP2 positioning trials;

- Vedia test vehicle;
- Enide: tracking app— potential extension.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials are performed in Vedia lab and in Otaniemi/Espoo/Finland VTT lab in order make preparations for ferry trials.

- Vedia office/lab (Helsinki) + VTT and Cumucore test lab (Otaniemi/Espoo): system preparation and pre-testing of set-up;
- Vedia will create the baseline data and large-scale trial capabilities in collaboration with UC5.1. partners in Espoo;
- test network testing VTT + Cumucore (Espoo).

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- test devices inside the ferry and access to ferry communication infra;
- 5G- ROUTES communication environment on the ferry and shore (including multi-hop and satellite);
- ferry transport between Finland and Estonia and related ports;
- second test vessel;
- IoT devices will be connected to Vedia CaaS cloud system, from where data can be shared for external usage;
- Vedia cloud servers will provide statistics and logs for parameters.

8. Location for field trials

- Ferry trip between Helsinki and Tallinn: Vuosaari – Muuga connection, where main test site is close to port of Vuosaari.

9. Logging of data and logging process

- Vedia VCU/OBU devices and 5G-mobile with Vedia app are supporting data logging inside ferry with time stamp (if 5G on board network delivers radio signal to cargo space as planned) to support the PI's and defined trials;
- communication infrastructure inside ferry, data logging with time stamp;
- vehicle: 5G-device ID data linked with data synch to OBU, 5G-phone, RSU, IoT devices and VCU data;
- VCU/OBU: data logging with time stamp;
- IoT devices/VCU: data logging with time stamp;
- connectivity infrastructure/network during ferry trip: data logging with time stamp.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

- Eckerö Line;
- Arctia secondary vessel provider;
- connectivity service providers (Cumucore, Digita,);
- relevant 5G ROUTES project partners (e.g VTT, Enide and Airbus);
- testing with Vedia own vehicles.

7.2.2 UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border

1. Use case

The use case aims to provide a continuous video communication between the ferry's staff, between the ferry and the harbour's administration to lead to a safe trip for the passengers and also video communication between two ferries. Lack of video communication between ferry staff and between two ferries at a cross border can possibly lead to human fatalities and damages to ferry in critical situations. Use case 5.2 focuses on the provision of live streaming services between the captain and the ferry's staff and between two ferries for a safe and smooth trip including cross border areas. UC 5.2 offers the ability to cover cross-border issues, including seamless communication of high bandwidth video streaming during the multihop communication between harbour to ferry and between ferry to another ferry and seamless video communication support to the captain throughout the trip.

Figure 17: Video live streaming between two ferries and between a ferry and a harbour

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

For the maritime technology there is a requirement to have a CAM service continuity along the whole ferry route and from one ferry to another especially when the ferries cross a border. Therefore, the 5G coverage along the route needs to be sufficient to provide service continuity. Additionally, inside the ferry, due to heavy iron construction, it is difficult to support the coverage, therefore the network coverage also inside the ferry needs to be sufficient.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

The 5G-ROUTES needs to provide good coverage in the sea route between ferries when they cross a border and good coverage inside the ferry to support the needed service continuity for video streaming applications between ferries and between a ferry and a harbour. The high data originated from the cameras and the CAM service interruption time at a cross border need to be measured:

- the data rate measured when the cameras connected to an OBU are transmitting between ferries and between a ferry and a harbour;
- service interruption time at a cross border.

4. Use case scenarios

This use case will first be tested in the local lab, then at VTT'S lab and finally at the ferry route. The roadmap is as follows:

Phase #1 trials

- Lab trial #1: video with high data rate sent from the camera of the OBU to test that the CAM service is operating;
- Lab trial #2: CAM service is tested at VTT where the OBU is operating inside a VAN and the CAM service remotely from a cloud server;

Phase #2 Trials

- Field trial #1: At this phase, video with high data rate DL and UL at a cross border in the sea will be tested.
- Field trial #2: for this trial along with the CAM service, 3-4 mobile terminals will populate the network with heavy traffic to test the effect on the network capability.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

- WINGS: Use case Leader. Developer of smart gateway and CAM video application in a server;
- Eckerö Line: Vediafi subcontractor, provides one ferry as test platform;
- Digita: communication devices on ferry;
- Digita: network provider for ferry;
- Cumucore: 5G Core;
- Arctia Ltd: second test vessel for field trials;
- Airbus: satellite communication for ferry.
-

6. Location for lab trials

The lab trials are performed at WINGS lab in Athens.

- Lab trials will be performed first at WINGS lab for testing eMBB type of traffic which will be followed with tests in VTT's lab.
- CAM service data rate measurements in WINGS lab;
- CAM service data rate measurements with a moving vehicle in VTT's lab

KPIs to be demonstrated at the maritime trials and validated:

- QoS degradation < 5% during cross-border mobility;
- Zero dropped sessions during cross-border mobility;
- Data rate downlink and uplink.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- 5G coverage throughout the ferry route;
- 5G testbed and network coverage inside the ferry and along the route;
- WINGS cloud servers will provide a UI for statistics and logs data.

8. Location for field trials

- Ferry trip from Helsinki to Tallinn.

9. Logging of data and logging process

- Live streaming data from the OBU, and application server will be logged for this CAM use case,
- OBU with video camera equipped;
- User interface to show the start of the application and KPIs values

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

End users such as professional and/or ferry passengers will take part in the use case testing/trials and will interact with the developed user interface (via laptops and/or smartphones). For confidentiality and ease of access purposes the people involved in the trials will be preferably employed by one of the project partners. A clear and understandable consent form will be provided to the human experimenters informing them about the data to be logged. Data logging follows GDPR guidelines and is anonymized to protect the privacy of the human experimenters. No specific information regarding each user will be collected besides their location (GPS data from smartphone or vehicle) and potential video recordings of the tests. As of that tests will involve the following partners:

- Eckerö Line;
- Port actors;
- Testing with Vedia's vehicles;
- WINGS OBU and application server.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable is the third report on the testing framework. Deliverable D1.7 gave an initial description of the test framework at the start of the project. Deliverable D1.12 provided an update, including the procedures for collecting data. This deliverable, D1.8, provides the final version of the testing framework.

The nature of the CAM use cases puts stringent requirements to the testing environment, especially for automated driving manoeuvres, like a closed traffic environment with multiple lanes covered by multiple networks.

The technical validation will be performed during the field trials, as well as a large-scale trial on the corridor Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki. However, due to changes in the project and delays in the availability of 5G SA roaming, only a single trial cycle is planned. This trial cycle will consist of two short phases: in a first phase, preliminary scenarios are tested, focusing on analysing the service disruption during cross-border handover and validating the integration of the use cases interaction with the CAM Services Platform in a real environment. In the second phase, the more complex use case scenarios will be evaluated.

The use cases are organised in two ecosystems: the terrestrial and the maritime ecosystem. The use cases from the terrestrial ecosystem will be trialled at the E265 border crossing in Valga/Valka and automated driving tests may be performed at a virtual crossing at the Bikernieki race track in Riga. The maritime use cases will be trialled on a ferry between Vuosaari and Muuga.

Based on the list of identified Performance Indicators (PIs), the data, which have to be logged, have been identified. Both use case agnostic data will be collected, as well as use case specific data. Data will be collected both at transport and at application level. The applications hence have to implement the required logging, for being able to calculate the PIs. In addition, all network elements have to be synchronised with each other, in order to be able to measure latencies accurately.

Collected data will be stored in the Tenant Web Portal, which is part of the 5G-ROUTES platform, and which is described in more detail in D2.7. The use case leaders will extract the data from the web for performing the analysis and calculate the PIs, which are then fed back in the Tenant Web Portal, where the composite indicators, defined in D1.9, are calculated and visualised.

The whole data chain, from data collection, importing and storing the collected data in the Tenant Web Portal, calculation of PIs and visualisation of composite indicators in the Tenant Web Portal, will be validated during the first set of lab tests, and refined before the first set of localised trials. Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment. The commercialisation validation process will create anticipatory business plans for two solutions that extend 5G for the different environments of cross-border. The business impact assessment will deliver the estimated impact and cost-benefit for the developed ecosystems, validated by both internal and external to the project stakeholders. Furthermore, on the basis of the 5G Architecture and 5G CAM Infrastructure developed in the project, the interoperability impact and deployment potential will be investigated in close collaboration with the project technology providers. Results of the business validation will be reported in the new D5.2 (merged D5.2 and D5.3) "Business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems".

9 References

- [1] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.1 Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0
- [2] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.3 Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0
- [3] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D1.5 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0
- [4] 5G-ROUTES (2023) D1.9 Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0
- [5] 5G-ROUTES (2023) D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0
- [6] 5G-ROUTES (2023) D1.12 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results, v2.0
- [7] 5G-ROUTES (2024) D1.2 Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM final version
- [8] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D5.1 Commercialisation marketing plan for 5G enabled business models for CAM v1.0
- [9] 5G-ROUTES (2023) D2.7 Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment v1
- [10] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM 1.0
- [11] 5G-ROUTES (2024) D4.1 Use Cases' field trials planning, setup and operational management handbook
- [12] 5G-SOLUTIONS, 5G-solutions for European Citizens, <https://www.5gsolutionsproject.eu/>
- [13] Deming, W. Edwards (1986). Out of the crisis. Cambridge, MA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for Advanced Engineering Study.
- [14] 5G-TOURS, <https://5gtours.eu/>
- [15] 5G-EVE, 5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials, <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>
- [16] 5G-MOBIX, Driving forward Connected & Automated Mobility, <https://www.5g-mobix.com/>
- [17] FESTA Handbook, Version 7 (2018, December), Retrieved from <https://connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/FESTA-Handbook-Version-7.pdf>
- [18] TRUSTS, Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space, <https://www.trusts-data.eu/>
- [19] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.1 AI-Assisted Cross-Domain MEC and Integration Fabric for CAM services v1.0
- [20] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.3 AI-based end-to-end slicing optimisation and innovative spectrum usage for CAM services v1.0
- [21] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological Enablers for CAM v1.0
- [22] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM
- [23] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D3.3 Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v1.0
- [24] Macharis C., Verbeke A., De Brucker K. (2004) The strategic evaluation of new technologies through Multicriteria analysis: the Advisors case, In: Bekiaris, E., Nakanishi Y. (Eds.), Economic Impacts of Intelligent Transportation Systems: Innovations and Case Studies. Research in Transportation Economics. Elsevier, Vol. 8, pp. 443–462.
- [25] ITU-R report M.2410-0 “Minimum requirements related to technical performance for IMT-2020
- [26] K. Katsaros et al. (2019) 5G-MOBIX D2.5, Initial evaluation KPIs and metrics. Retrieved from <https://www.5g-mobix.com/assets/files/5G-MOBIX-D2.5-Initial-evaluation-KPIs-and-metrics-V1.4.pdf>
- [27] 5G for Europe: An Action Plan. European Commission, SWD (2016), 306.
- [28] European Commission (2019), STRIA Roadmap on Connected and Automated Transport: Road, Rail and Waterborne, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation.
- [29] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D5.7 Data Management Plan v1.0
- [30] 5G-MOBIX (2022) D3.7 Final Report on Development, Integration and Roll-out
- [31] Kaitotek (2022) Qosium, <https://www.kaitotek.com/qosium>

- [32] De Brucker, K., Macharis, C. (2011), Best Things First. The Application of Multi-Criteria Analysis to Derive Implementation Priorities for Innovative Road Safety Measures. *Infrastructure and Safety in a Collaborative World*, pp. 305-325
- [33] Keysight (2023), Nemo Outdoor 5G NR Drive Test Solution, <https://www.keysight.com/fi/en/product/NTA50000B/nemo-outdoor-5g-nr-drive-test-solution.html>
- [34] ETSI TS 138 331-V16.13.0 (2023) 5G; NR; Radio Resource Control (RRC); Protocol specification (3GPP TS 38.331 version 16.13.0 Release 16)
- [35] ITU-R report M.2410-0 "Minimum requirements related to technical performance for IMT-2020"
- [36] "Definition of the Testing Framework for the NGMN 5G Pre-Commercial Networks Trials" https://www.ngmn.org/wp-content/uploads/Publications/2019/190802_NGMN-PreCommTrials_Framework_definition_v3.0.pdf
- [37] ITU-R report M.2410-0 "Minimum requirements related to technical performance for IMT-2020"
- [38] 5G PPP, "5G PPP Phase II KPIs," Report, Jan. 2019
- [39] 3GPP TS 28.554 "5G end to end Key Performance Indicators"
- [40] NGMN, "A deliverable by the NGMN alliance – NGMN 5G white paper," https://www.ngmn.org/fileadmin/ngmn/content/images/news/ngmn_news/NGMN_5G_White_Paper_V1_0.pdf
- [41] KPI Requirements for Next Generation Access Technologies <http://www.techplayon.com/kpi-requirements-for-next-generation-access-technologies/>